

Deliverable 5.3

Dissemination and Communication Plan and Results – Interim version

White Research
February 2024

R **BIN**

**DEPLOYING CIRCULAR BIOECONOMIES AT
REGIONAL LEVEL WITH A TERRITORIAL APPROACH**

Funded by
the European Union

PROJECT INFORMATION

PROGRAMME	Horizon Europe
TOPIC	HORIZON-CL6-2021-GOVERNANCE-01
TYPE OF ACTION	HORIZON-CSA
PROJECT NUMBER	101060504
START DAY	1 September 2022
DURATION	36 months

DOCUMENT INFORMATION

TITLE	Dissemination and Communication Plan and Results – Interim version
WORK PACKAGE	5
TASK	T5.1 Dissemination, Communication and Stakeholder Engagement
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DATE	27.02.2024

DISSEMINATION LEVEL

PU	Public, fully open	x
SEN	Sensitive, limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement	

DOCUMENT HISTORY

Version	Date	Changes	Responsible partner
v0.1	16.2.2024	Initial	WR
v0.2	23.2.2024	Internal review of the deliverable	QPL, AUTH, ZSK
v0.3	27.2.2024	Updated version of the deliverable	WR
v1.0	29.2.2024	Submission to the European Commission	QPL

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ABBREVIATIONS

DCP	Dissemination and Communication Plan
CCRI-CSO	Circular Cities and Regions Initiative – Coordination and Support Office
D&C	Dissemination and Communication Strategy
SMA_s	Social Media Accounts
SRA	Southern Regional Assembly
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
PO	Project Officer
MARC	Multi-Actor Regional Constellations
AB	Advisory Board

This project has used a standard methodology already developed in INCENTIVE project (Grant Agreement number: 101005330), following EU recommendations. Ad hoc modifications were added to comply with the Grant Agreement conditions for ROBIN (Grant Agreement number: 101060504)

Executive summary

This report constitutes the updated version of the **Deliverable 5.1 Dissemination and Communication Plan (DCP) – Initial version** of the Horizon Europe ROBIN project (GA 101060504). This document is the **Deliverable 5.3 Dissemination and Communication Plan and Results – Interim version** and provides comprehensive details on all aspects of ROBIN's communication and dissemination strategy up to February 2024 (Month 18). It presents the communication tools and channels which are being used to maximize ROBIN's visibility and the progress of the project over the first 18 months in terms of dissemination Key Performance Indicators (KPIs).

Most of the chapters included in this report are updated versions of the Initial version of the DCP, already submitted in November 2022 (M3), and are organised as follows:

- Chapter 1: An introduction to the DCP and its goals.
- Chapter 2: A brief description of the ROBIN project.
- Chapter 3: An overview of the Dissemination and Communication (D&C) Strategy and its objectives.
- Chapter 4: The targeted audiences and the respective key messages for the identified stakeholders.
- Chapter 5: The tools and channels used to disseminate and communicate the project's activities and results to the identified targeted stakeholders.
- Chapter 6: The roles and responsibilities of the dissemination manager and the consortium partners for the successful deployment of the D&C strategy.
- Chapter 7: The importance of establishing synergies with other relevant projects and networks throughout the duration of the project is elaborated on in this chapter.
- Chapter 8: The progress on setting up and operating ROBIN's Advisory Board.
- Chapter 9: The KPIs progress and the reporting process regarding the dissemination activities.
- Chapter 10: The timeline of the four different stages for the implementation of the project's dissemination activities is briefly described in this section.
- Chapter 11: The conclusions of the updated DCP and the next steps.

The Annexes include:

- The dissemination and communication reporting template: This is the template that all partners need to update on a monthly basis with information about all the dissemination and communication activities.
- The collaboration agreement template.

In the first half of the project, ROBIN's communication and dissemination actions reached over 152.000 stakeholders. According to metrics, more than half of the stakeholders reached through our regular social media posts and regional awareness-raising campaigns for our co-creation workshops which took place during the first year of ROBIN, while a significant percentage came from the scientific community, industry and policy area. Analysis of the metrics also suggests that the three most effective dissemination channels so far have been:

(i) participation in various external events, conferences and webinars, (ii) regional workshops, and (iii) regular social media posts and dissemination of results on the ROBIN website. The evaluation of the engagement activities presented in this report clearly indicates that ROBIN's consortium has successfully raised awareness among the targeted stakeholders. This has created a solid foundation of local audiences in the five pilot regions helping the ROBIN team to promote further the deployment of circular bioeconomy strategies with a territorial approach. Continuous efforts and monitoring of the performed activities are needed to maintain this momentum and achieve the aims of the DCP for the following 18 months of the project.

1. Introduction

It is essential to disseminate and communicate the project's vision and results effectively to ensure the successful implementation of the ROBIN project. In this context, this deliverable presents the updated version of the DCP, describes the operational framework for its deployment, and provides an overview of the results achieved so far in ROBIN's dissemination and communication strategy.

The main objective of ROBIN's Dissemination and Communication (D&C) Strategy is to define the actions carried out and the tools to be used for the promotion of the project's results. On top of that, the strategy presented in D5.1 provided a specific plan to raise awareness around the project and support ROBIN's implementation. Thus, besides supporting the exploitation of ROBIN outcomes, the DCP ensures the sustainability of the assets developed during the project's lifecycle.

In particular, the DCP offers the answers to some fundamental questions about the communication and dissemination activities of the project:

Table 1. Summary of D&C's key questions

Key questions	ROBIN's DCP
What?	Key messages
To Whom?	Target audiences
Who?	Roles & Responsibilities
How?	Communication tools and channels, guidelines, and templates
When?	Timeline

As stated in D5.1, the guidelines, templates, and annexes produced in the report are subject to updates in line with the project's progress. The experience and lessons learned throughout the implementation of the project will permit the team to update and modify the strategy, when needed, to be tailored to the needs of their vision. The final version of the D&C strategy is already foreseen by M36 and ensures the continuation of the dissemination of the results even after the completion of ROBIN.

2. About ROBIN project

Europe's regional authorities have a crucial role to play as agents of inclusive and resilient economic development for their territories. ROBIN sets out to empower them to fulfill this role with support to co-shape their governance structures to accelerate the deployment of their circular bioeconomy targets, while also promoting social innovation. The ROBIN project demonstrates the potential of innovative circular bioeconomy governance structures and models in 5 regions within Ireland, Germany, Spain, Slovakia, and Greece. ROBIN's team will set up Multi-Actor Regional Constellations engaging key stakeholders to co-create novel governance structures, well-embedded within existing structures of our regions and mandated to execute circular bioeconomy strategies and to coordinate effectively with the Circular Cities and Regions Initiative – Coordination and

Support Office (CCRI-CSO). The multidisciplinary consortium of ROBIN will provide the regions with tailored support for enhanced stakeholder engagement, as well as a practical toolbox to improve the operation and monitoring of their models. In the process, ROBIN coordinates its actions with the CCRI-CSO.

The ambition of the EU-funded, ROBIN project is to accelerate the deployment of circular bioeconomy at the regional level in 5 European pilot regions. The project's goal is to support the adaptation of governance models through multi-stakeholder engagement and coordination and promote social innovation.

Thus, the overall objectives of the ROBIN project are:

- ✓ Deeper understanding of existing bioeconomy governance practices and models in Europe
- ✓ Enhanced understanding of the bioeconomy's benefits amongst all stakeholders (including primary biomass producers as well as consumers)
- ✓ Improved regional governance models with increased stakeholder engagement accelerating the circular bioeconomy transition of European regions
- ✓ Better informed bioeconomy strategies creating conducive conditions for investments in sustainable business opportunities offered by local bio-based economies
- ✓ Improved environmental footprint of bio-based products and services
- ✓ Increased cross-regional coordination under the CCRI reinforcing the EU science-policy interface for addressing Sustainable Development Goals

Within the next years, the multidisciplinary consortium of the ROBIN project will organise several events and workshops to inform the audience about important findings and updates on the progress of the project.

Lastly, the dimension of sustainability is pivotal to the goals of the project. As such, the dissemination and communication efforts are vital for the maximisation of its impact and value extraction. Creating multiple channels for taking advantage of the project assets is a key priority for ROBIN and it becomes apparent that dissemination and communication activities are significant, as they leverage the sustainability of the project's positive impacts.

3. Dissemination and communication strategy

3.1. Overview

The initial DCP of ROBIN (submitted in M3) described the overall D&C strategy of the project concerning the dissemination and communication of its outcomes. The strategy was carefully designed and tailored to the approach of the project aiming to maximise its impact, transfer knowledge and the results to the targeted stakeholders, as well as to communicate its concept to wider audiences. ROBIN's D&C strategy is constantly being translated into a robust plan by considering multiple key elements as illustrated in the figure 1 below and described in the next chapters.

Figure 1. Overview of ROBIN's D&C strategy

This section presents the overview of the D&C strategy and introduces briefly the structure of the DCP already set in M3. The first sub-section of this chapter presents the objectives of the DCP which are used to monitor the successful implementation of the strategy. The next chapter defines the target audience i.e., to whom are disseminated the project's results. On top of that, the next sub-section presents the key messages for each one of the targeted stakeholders, as well as the core visions and assets. A dedicated section of the strategy focuses on the means, channels, and tools that are used to reach the identified stakeholders. Additionally, the allocation of roles and responsibilities for the dissemination strategy are clearly elaborated to ensure the smooth and effective implementation of the DCP.

Throughout the duration of the project, special attention has been and will continue to be given to cooperation with other relevant projects at national and European levels. Although there is a dedicated task (T5.3) for establishing synergies with other relevant projects and networks, the document presents a short introduction regarding the initial plan. Lastly, the next chapters unveil a robust framework for the assessment of the strategy along with a timeline for the dissemination and communication steps.

Aiming to ensure the successful dissemination and communication of results, the DCP constitutes a guiding document that presents the tools and actions which will navigate the consortium partners to successfully engage the targeted stakeholders. Of course, the DCP is dynamic and flexible, meaning that it can be reviewed and updated - if this is necessary - during the project's lifecycle.

3.2. Objectives of the DCP

The initial version of the D&C strategy of ROBIN has set a list of practical and realistic objectives that ensured the effective monitoring and consequently the successful implementation of the dissemination and communication activities of the project. Along the way of the project's lifecycle, new objectives have been added that match the needs that emerged during the first 18 months of ROBIN.

The objectives answer the question of WHY the DCP is needed. The existing and new dissemination and communication objectives of ROBIN are briefly presented below:

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- Present the project's aim, vision, activities, and events to a wider audience;
- Promote awareness raising among stakeholder groups;
- Encourage involvement in the project's activities;
- Engage stakeholders through a series of relevant activities, events, and conferences;
- Ensure that the key messages are communicated to its target audiences;
- Ensure the exploitation of the project's outcomes;
- Plan, organise, monitor, and fine-tune the project's dissemination activities and events;
- Establish and sustain synergies with other relevant national and European projects and networks;
- Disseminate the project's lessons learned and outcomes in an open and transparent way;
- Support the visibility and engagement activities of ROBIN's pilot regions; (new)
- Store all project's key outcomes and results on ROBIN's website; (new)
- Disseminate key outcomes and results through ROBIN's SMAs; (new)
- Promote open access to ROBIN's deliverables and data. (new)

Four new objectives have been added to the DCP. The first one concerns the holistic support of all engagement and dissemination activities in ROBIN's pilot regions. This support includes a series of actions, such as the preparation of tailored dissemination materials, drafting and publishing of articles outlining the process and progress of the co-creation workshops, as well as promoting them. The second new objective relates to archiving all of the project's key outcomes and results on ROBIN's website, while the third one focuses on the dissemination of these outcomes through the project's SMAs. The final new objective pertains to the promotion of open access practices for all of ROBIN's deliverables and data.

4. Target audience and key messages

4.1. Target audience

One of the most critical steps for the successful development of the D&C strategy is to answer the question “to Whom?”. Who are the main stakeholders that the project aims to engage and transfer its messages and results to? This section presents the main target audiences that have benefited from the project. The figure below briefly presents the target audiences:

Figure 2. ROBIN target audiences

ROBIN has already engaged a wide variety of stakeholders with different backgrounds and experiences and will continue doing so. In particular it has engaged:

1. Policy actors (Directorate Generals of the European Commission, EU policymakers, National governments, Local governments, Regional authorities, Policy advisors)
2. Civil society (consumers, clusters & action groups)
3. Researchers & academia
4. Horizon projects, CCRI projects & other EU initiatives
5. Regional bioeconomy actors (e.g., primary biomass producers)
6. Bio-based SMEs & Industries (e.g., biobased industrial companies)
7. Innovation & policy advisors
8. Financial Institutions
9. Bioeconomy Experts
10. General public
11. International Organisations

During the project’s lifespan, it remains important to classify them to better prioritise and fine-tune our engagement efforts. To this aim, the Stakeholders Classification Model¹ is used in order to classify each targeted stakeholder group based on the following parameters:

- The extent of a stakeholder’s power/authority;
- The stakeholder’s interest regarding the outcomes of the project;
- The extent of the stakeholder’s active involvement in the project;
- The level of stakeholder’s influence over the project planning and/or outcomes.

Figure 3. Stakeholder mapping and types of stakeholder engagement

The D&C strategy aims to reach the above-mentioned identified audiences which were further categorised into the broader ROBIN stakeholder groups. A more detailed elaboration on the targeted stakeholders and specific examples are offered in the following Table:

Table 2. ROBIN target audience categories

Target Group	Short description	Sub-categories
Policy actors	Decision-makers at European, national, and regional levels that are expected to play a key role in policy design.	Directorate Generals of the European Commission EU policymakers National governments Local governments Regional authorities Policy advisors
Bioeconomy industry & actors	All actors that are active in the field of bioeconomy and regional development.	Biobased SMEs Bioeconomy experts Biobased industrial companies

¹ Emerson Wagner Mainardes, Helena Alves, Mário Raposo, (2012). “A model for stakeholder classification and stakeholder relationships”, Management Decision, Vol. 50 Issue: 10, pp. 1861-1879.

		Innovation Advisors Investors Regional bioeconomy actors Primary biomass producers
Scientific community	Network of interacting scientists who conduct research in the fields of bioeconomy, regional development, and biobased products	Research Centres Research groups Individual researchers Universities
Civil Society	Individuals who are interested in enhancing their knowledge of bioeconomy, biobased products	General public Consumers Clusters Action Groups
Relevant EU projects, CCRI & other EU initiatives	Horizon Europe and Horizon 2020 projects as well as other European and national projects and initiatives	CCRI H2020 projects Horizon Europe projects Other EU-funded projects (e.g., Interreg, Erasmus+)
Organisations & Institutions	Organisations (governmental and non-governmental) and Institutions that are active in the bioeconomy field	International Organisations NGOs Financial Institutions Governmental Institutions

4.2. Key messages and vision

4.2.1. Key messages

Another important step for establishing a successful D&C strategy is to determine WHAT will be communicated to the stakeholders. In the previous section, the first identification of the most critical stakeholder groups to be reached in the framework of the project was presented. These groups consist of stakeholders with different backgrounds and needs, therefore different messages should be communicated to them. These messages might be updated over the course of the project based on the experience acquired during the implementation of the activities. Furthermore, the project has been already exploiting the extended network of consortium partners in order to reach a wide pool of individuals and will continue to do so.

Table 3 lists the targeted stakeholder groups along with their needs and tailored messages. So far, the initial key needs & messages identified since the beginning of ROBIN, have been working effectively for ROBIN's D&C strategy. However, the final key messages will be defined throughout the project's lifecycle based on the actual ROBIN data and outcomes.

Table 3. ROBIN target audience, needs and messages

Target Group	Needs	Messages
<p style="writing-mode: vertical-rl; transform: rotate(180deg);">Policy actors</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Understand the current landscape of regional bioeconomy governance models – Explore new ways of establishing regional governance models with a focus on bioeconomy – Better informed and effective policies for developing regional governance models with a focus on bioeconomy – Explore new ways of engaging stakeholders from different backgrounds – Develop new regional strategies – Integrate social innovation into the policy development process – More examples of applied best practices and how to replicate them – Enhance the knowledge of how to coordinate CCRI actions with EU-funded projects – Achieve progress toward meeting regional, national, and EU policy targets – Introduce a more socio-economic and environmental approach to the development of regional governance models 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Increased policy recommendations on how to create regional bioeconomy models ✓ Enhanced engagement of stakeholders in bioeconomy models ✓ Improved, more inclusive, and better-informed governance models based on stakeholder engagement ✓ Further insights on local potentialities along with the means to tap into them for stimulating bio-based and social innovation ✓ Increased support to raise awareness amongst regional bioeconomy stakeholders and engage them in building and improving governance models
<p style="writing-mode: vertical-rl; transform: rotate(180deg);">Bioeconomy industry & actors</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Increase the market penetration of biobased innovations – Develop bio-based value chains that deliver sustainable products/ services – Capitalise on emerging investment opportunities in bio-based sectors 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Increased networking and stakeholder engagement opportunities to build connections required to accelerate bio-based innovation ✓ Enhanced integration of bio-based value chain development into broader policies and regional development plans ✓ Increased awareness of bioeconomy and its benefits ✓ Increased demand for bio-based products/services

<p>Scientific community</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Advance research in focal scientific fields related to bioeconomy – Keep in line with industry and policy developments in the bioeconomy field – Follow recent developments and research trends – Identify research gaps for further research 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Aggregation and classification of existing scientific knowledge of types of bioeconomy governance models ✓ New knowledge and empirical open data on the application of novel inclusive governance models
<p>Society</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Increased socioeconomic and environmental benefits from established policies – Plethora of more sustainable, healthier, and affordable products and services 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ A more meaningful engagement in regional bioeconomy governance and policy making ✓ Increased understanding of the bioeconomy and how to make better-informed and more sustainable choices.
<p>Relevant EU projects, CCRI & other EU initiatives</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Exchange knowledge with other experts in the field – Share their results and promote their concept to other initiatives and the general public – Establish synergies and expand their network 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Deliverables with the project results to enhance further research in the field ✓ A network of synergies that facilitates collaboration and knowledge transfer between relevant initiatives ✓ Increased support in the dissemination of the project's results
<p>Organisations & Institutions</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Stay updated regarding the latest developments in the bioeconomy and policy development field – Engage and inform more citizens about social innovative governance structures on bioeconomy – Stay informed about the progress regarding the establishment of regional bioeconomy models 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Ways to integrate best practices derived from the project into the development of regional bioeconomy models

The abovementioned messages are subject to change to reflect the actual needs of stakeholders, as identified during the first engagement activities of the project. The final key messages will be updated and refined throughout the project based on the experience acquired during its implementation.

5. Communication and dissemination tools and channels

ROBIN's DCP employs a range of tools and channels to ensure that its activities and produced outcomes reach a diverse set of stakeholders, thereby contributing to the adoption of circular bioeconomies at the regional level. An overview of the different tools, channels, and dissemination activities is presented in Figure 4, showcasing HOW the D&C strategy is implemented.

Figure 4. ROBIN's communication activities

ROBIN'S promotional material and graphical identity include:

- Project logo
- Project's visual and graphical identity
- Leaflet
- Poster
- Templates (e.g., for publications and presentations)
- Letterhead
- Ad-hoc promotional material (tailored to the project's activities and needs – if needed)

ROBIN'S online presence includes:

- Website
- Bi-annual newsletters
- Facebook page
- Twitter account
- LinkedIn profile
- YouTube channel
- Promotional video

ROBIN'S events include:

- Engagement events
- Participation in external events and conferences as ROBIN representatives
- Final dissemination event
- Co- organisation and participation in events with projects that we have established synergies (e.g., webinars, workshops, joint Final Conference)

ROBIN'S publications include:

- Project's deliverables
- Scientific publications
- Other publications in different media (e.g., articles, press releases, etc.)

The following sub-chapters present a detailed description of the abovementioned tools and channels.

5.1. Promotional material (updated)

The promotional material of ROBIN was prepared during the early stages of the project. WR was responsible for the graphic design and the content, while the consortium partners offered feedback throughout the development process. The material has been made freely available for download to the public on the project's website [here](#), as well as on ROBIN's online Teams and SharePoint repositories, so that partners can download, print and distribute them when needed. All promotional material can be and are already being used during physical activities (including external and project events) to attract and engage relevant stakeholders and provide more information on the project's mission and objectives.

All the promotional material is designed based on the project's unique identity which is presented in the following paragraph.

5.1.1. Project logo (updated)

The early design of the graphical identity of ROBIN in terms of the project's logo and templates have ensured consistency throughout the project. Therefore, the project's logo and visual identity have already been developed (M1) to satisfy the visual requirements of the project. The logo makes the project recognisable and forms the basis for the design of all the promotional material, which are used for the different promotional and communication materials (e.g., leaflets, posters, newsletters, deliverables, social media, web-portal, publications, publicity for internal and external events, etc.).

During the kick-off meeting of the project, various logo options were presented to the partners to state their preferences and select their favorite design. WR presented the different options to partners, which in turn voted online on their preference. Taking into consideration partners' preferences, WR opted for the more popular logo. The final logo is presented in Figure 5.

Figure 5. ROBIN project logo

The design of the logo reflects the project’s concept. The green leaves symbolise the bioeconomy element and the gear the circular economy. The logo also includes the phrase: “Deploying Circular Bioeconomies at Regional level with a Territorial Approach” which presents ROBIN’s overall concept and vision. The logo’s color palette includes brown and green tints which represent the earth and natural resources which are fundamental to many bioeconomy initiatives.

Figure 6. ROBIN's colour palette

The ROBIN logo should be visible to all the communication material produced in the framework of the project (presentation, deliverables, etc.). Similarly, the EU funding should be properly acknowledged, and the EU emblem should also be properly depicted in all communication material.

Figure 7. EU funding statement

5.1.2. Leaflet and poster (updated)

A trifold leaflet and a poster were prepared to be distributed by the partners in physical events and activities but also to be uploaded on the project’s website. Both the poster and leaflet are used to attract stakeholders’ attention and provide brief information about the ROBIN project.

The leaflet presents the project’s aim to empower Europe’s regions to adapt their governance models and structures in ways that accelerate the achievement of their circular bioeconomy targets while promoting social innovation and accounting for different territorial contexts. The poster focuses more on attracting the stakeholders’ attention with graphical elements and offers some basic information on the project and the key stakeholder groups.

D5.3: Dissemination and Communication Plan and Results – Interim version

Both items provide information about the partners involved, together with contact, website and SMAs details as well as acknowledge the funding the project receives through the Horizon Europe program.

The initial draft versions of the project’s leaflet and poster are illustrated in Figure 8, respectively.

Figure 8. The front and back side of the initial version of ROBIN leaflet

Figure 8. The initial version of ROBIN poster

To accommodate some needs that emerged during ROBIN’s first 18 months of life (e.g., the change of logo of ROBIN’s partner Southern Regional Assembly (SRA), the official change of Twitter’s logo) and to increase the project’s visibility and provide easy access to ROBIN’s website and promotional material, the initial version of ROBIN’s leaflet and poster have been updated in M13. Consequently, the promotional material which have been updated with **SRA’s new logo**, **Twitter’s new logo** and a **QR-Code** are presented below.

The project

ROBIN aims to empower Europe's regions to adapt their governance models and structures in ways that accelerate the achievement of their circular bioeconomy targets while promoting social innovation and accounting for different territorial contexts.

IT WILL SUPPORT 5 REGIONAL AUTHORITIES ACROSS EUROPE TO:

- adapt their governance models to support the scaling up of the bio-based value chains of their ecosystem
- exploit existing knowledge from earlier work and knowhow in bioeconomy policy and social innovation
- network and source knowledge from peers and consort with the European Commission's Circular Cities and Regions Initiative's Coordination and Support Office (CCRI-CSO).

OUR TEAM

	Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL ADVISORS PC www.qplan-intl.gr
	FUNDACION CORPORACION TECNOLOGICA DE ANDALUCIA www.corporaciontecnologica.com
	WHITE RESEARCH SRL www.white-research.eu
	PEDAL CONSULTING SRO www.pedal-consulting.eu
	STEINBEIS 21 GMBH www.steinbeis-europa.de
	ROZVOJOVA AGENCIA ZILINSKEHO SAMOSPRAVNEHO KRAJA NO www.razsk.sk
	MUNSTER TECHNOLOGICAL UNIVERSITY www.cirobio.ie
	ARISTOTELIO PANEPISTIMIO THESSALONIKIS www.auth.gr
	REGION OF CENTRAL MACEDONIA www.pkm.gov.mk
	CONSEJERÍA DE AGRICULTURA, PESCA, AGUA Y DESARROLLO RURAL www.juntadeandalucia.es
	INSTITUTO ANDALUZ DE INVESTIGACION Y FORMACION AGRARIA PESQUERA ALIMENTARIA Y DE LA PRODUCCION ECOLOGICA www.juntadeandalucia.es
	BIOPRO BADEN-WUERTEMBERG GMBH www.bio-pro.de
	SOUTHERN REGIONAL ASSEMBLY www.southernassembly.ie

ROBIN

DEPLOYING CIRCULAR BIOECONOMIES AT REGIONAL LEVEL WITH A TERRITORIAL APPROACH

www.robin-project.eu

PROJECT ID

PROJECT NAME: ROBIN
"Deploying circular bioeconomies at regional level with a territorial approach"

GRANT AGREEMENT: 101060504

PROGRAMME: Horizon Europe

TYPE OF ACTION: HORIZON-CSA

START DATE: 1 September 2022

DURATION: 36 months

EU CONTRIBUTION: 2,499,951,00€

COORDINATOR: Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL ADVISORS PC

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Funded by the European Union

The Challenge

Europe's regional authorities can play a crucial role in the socioeconomic development of their local ecosystems; yet, most of European regions are still exploring their position concerning bioeconomy. Bioeconomy can be a key pillar when it comes to a more circular and sustainable ways of development and Europe's regional governments should adapt their governance models and structures to enable practical applications of bioeconomy-related knowledge and advances. The newest policy mandates in the field of circularity increase the complexity of needed and expects actions for an integrated transition; however recently, high-quality knowledge has been developed to guide the bioeconomy transition.

Territorial approach

A territorial approach is followed in the deployment of circular bio-economies at regional level, which enables to:

- Focus on functional distribution of space based on degree of rurality / urbanisation (rural – semi rural – peri-urban – urban)
- Examine the natural, geographical, economic, social, political features of the region
- Examine the central control and the hierarchical organisation of networks within space
- Examine how the regional ecosystem is affected by spatial planning policies (regional development plans, urban development plans, etc)

ROBIN

DEPLOYING CIRCULAR BIOECONOMIES AT REGIONAL LEVEL WITH A TERRITORIAL APPROACH

www.robin-project.eu

OUR OBJECTIVES

- Deeper understanding of existing bioeconomy governance practices and models in Europe
- Enhanced understanding of the bioeconomy's benefits amongst all stakeholders (including primary biomass producers as well as consumers)
- Improved regional governance models with increased stakeholder engagement accelerating the circular bioeconomy transition of European regions
- Better informed bioeconomy strategies creating conducive conditions for investments in sustainable business opportunities offered by local bio-based economies
- Improved environmental footprint of bio-based products and services
- Increased cross-regional coordination under the CCRI reinforcing the EU science-policy interface for addressing Sustainable Development Goals

5 steps to innovative circular bioeconomy governance structures and models in the ROBIN Regions

STEP 1
Set the scene on regional bioeconomy governance models
ROBIN explores the existing governance models in Europe, develops a typology of these models and identifies good governance practices. It deepens the knowledge around the barriers, challenges and opportunities for the uptake of circular bioeconomy governance models through consultation with and active engagement of regional quadruple helix stakeholder representatives included in the Multi-Actor Regional Constellations (MARCs) of the project.

STEP 2
Co-create regional governance models and structures
Through a bottom-up approach, ROBIN engages the MARCs to co create governance models that overcome barriers and seize opportunities for circular bioeconomy. Moreover, it develops a practical Toolbox that contains actionable knowledge, a portfolio of coordination and support actions and user-friendly tools.

STEP 3
Set up and validate the ROBIN Toolbox
ROBIN deploys the ROBIN Toolbox within diverse territorial contexts across 5 European regions aiming at supporting the development and operation of governance models towards circular bioeconomy transition. The diversity of pilot regions in terms of socioeconomic, institutional and ecological features enable the replication of results.

STEP 4
Monitor & Evaluate results – Share of best practices
ROBIN exchanges best practices among regions, to promote the development of cross-regional partnerships on regional bioeconomy, transfer knowledge and experiences, build partnerships and enhance openness, transparency and engagement. Also, it develops an integrated replication guideline with the generated knowledge and tools which are validated through a robust monitoring and evaluation framework.

STEP 5
Communicate & Deploy synergies
ROBIN supports the dissemination and communication of its results through a tailored strategy involving the set-up of ROBIN Advisory Board, while also creating synergies with key European and national networks, as well as the Circular Cities and Regions Initiative – Coordination and Support Office (CCRI-CSO).

Figure 9. The front and back side of the updated version of ROBIN leaflet

Figure 10. The updated version of ROBIN poster

ROBIN’s website visitors are able to easily download the leaflet and the poster.

5.1.3. Publication templates (updated)

Besides the poster and the leaflet, templates have also been prepared in line with the graphical identity of the project to be used during dissemination activities. The developed templates include:

- The ROBIN .ppt presentation template (to be used by the consortium partners during events and meetings);
- Reports template (to be used for the project’s deliverables and other publications);
- Letterhead (to be used for official invitations to events).

The initial presentation and reports template are presented in Figure 13 and Figure 14, respectively.

Figure 11. ROBIN .ppt presentation template

Figure 12. ROBIN reports template

Similar to ROBIN's leaflet and poster, the .ppt template has been updated to incorporate SRA's new logo. The updated template is presented below:

Figure 13. Updated ROBIN .ppt presentation template

All partners should use the official project's templates when preparing presentations or reports in the framework of the project.

5.1.4. Letterhead (new)

In addition to the abovementioned templates, and as part of the promotional materials prepared, WR provided a letterhead to be used for official invitations to various project activities.

Figure 14. ROBIN letterhead

5.1.5. Promotional video (updated)

The promotional video of the project was produced in M9. The video presents briefly and in an animated way the project, its objectives, and future outcomes.

The video creation process is described as follows. First, a video script was prepared, which included the video's sequence and key phrases explaining the project's objectives, ROBIN's aims, and approach. All partners provided valuable feedback to enhance the script. After incorporating partners' comments and suggestions, the initial storyboard was ready. By providing feedback and suggestions for improvement once more, the storyboard was finalised, and the animated final version was completed.

The video aims to reach a broad audience through social networks. It has been uploaded to the project's YouTube channel [here](#), the project's website [here](#), and shared on all ROBIN's SMAs. The purpose of the promotional video is to introduce the viewer to the project in an understandable and engaging manner. Many terms and concepts used in the project, such as 'Quadruple Helix Stakeholders,' 'governance models,' 'bioeconomy practices,' etc., are not widely known, so it is crucial to communicate them at the EU level in a simple and accessible manner, encouraging viewers to engage with the project.

In terms of content, the video follows a narrative approach, featuring elements that describe ROBIN's approach and assets. The diversity of characters reflects the project's inclusive vision. This approach is designed to be welcoming and inclusive, making the project accessible to a broad audience, regardless of their familiarity with bioeconomy and regional governance models. Subtitles have been added in all ROBIN's pilot regions languages; Greek, Spanish, Slovakian, and German to cater to the audiences of all pilot regions. The video's duration is limited to 2 minutes and 20 seconds to maintain the viewer's attention. Finally, to enhance accessibility for an international audience, the amount of written text has been kept to a minimum, considering that not all viewers may be fluent in English. The following figures present some screenshots of ROBIN's promotional video.

Figure 15. ROBIN's promotional video screenshots

Table 4. Overview of promotional video KPI

Dissemination KPI	Target (M36)	Current status (M18)
Views of promotional video	>500	363

5.1.6. Other promotional material (updated)

To enhance its dissemination and communication outreach, ROBIN’s dissemination and communication team has created additional promotional materials to maximize the project’s visibility. These materials consist of:

- A general ROBIN presentation which introduces the project, its aim and objectives and can be used and customized by all partners to align with the specific requirements of their dissemination efforts (Figure 19).

Figure 16. ROBIN's general presentation

- A ROBIN QR code, which can direct users to the project's website and can also be integrated into any dissemination materials and presentations created by the partners for easy website access (Figure 20).

Figure 17. ROBIN QR code

- A promotional banner designed for maximising the project's visibility in both internal and external events (Figure 19).

Figure 18. ROBIN's promotional banner

5.2 Digital tools (updated)

Gradually, more people select to get informed through digital communication channels. To better communicate its messages, ROBIN focuses on building a strong online presence on multiple digital platforms aiming to reach as many diverse stakeholders as possible. In particular, ROBIN has created:

- (i) a website;
- (ii) bi-annual newsletters;
- (iii) various SMAs.

5.2.1.ROBIN website (updated)

The ROBIN website is a key tool for enhancing visibility. As described in the initial version of the Dissemination and Communication plan D5.1, an initial draft website structure was presented (Figure 22). The structure constituted a baseline for the website and will be updated, when necessary, to be in line with the project’s requirements and progress.

Figure 19. Initial draft website structure

The website became operational in M5 (January 2023) and has since served as the online platform for disseminating news and updates. The website's structure and content have been designed for user-friendliness and to clearly convey the project's concept, pilot universities, and objectives. Additionally, the website contains key information about the project's progress, including news and event announcements, to keep stakeholders informed. Rather than targeting a specific audience, the website works as a dynamic repository of project information and news, making it an online platform for reaching out to a broad range of stakeholders. WR is the partner responsible for the website's development, maintenance, and technical management, as well as overseeing web editing and content development. The website's URL is <https://robin-project.eu/>, and the project's contact email aligns with it (info@robin-project.eu).

Although WR, as the dissemination manager, will be the main responsible for the website management and content, all partners contribute to the content development with news and other dissemination material. The website will remain active throughout the duration of the project and includes regular updates on the project's progress, internal and external events, relevant projects and initiatives, reports and project results, as well as other news from the bioeconomy field.

The website was developed using WordPress. Special attention was given to creating a responsive and accessible website, ensuring compatibility with various devices, including mobile ones, to prevent the exclusion of potential stakeholders. The website includes some general information about the project and dedicated sections to present the team members and the members of the Advisory Board, all project outcomes such as public reports, dissemination material, and newsletters are (also available for downloading) and a dedicated section for the pilot regions as the territorial approach and Multi-Actor Regional Constellations are a key asset of the project. It also includes a dedicated section which redirects the user to the ROBIN's Toolbox. The project's Privacy and Cookies Policy is available on the website.

More specifically the website is presented below:

- **ROBIN Homepage;**

Figure 20. ROBIN's website homepage

- **Key information about the ROBIN concept and approach;**

Figure 21. About ROBIN website section

<p>Territorial Approach</p> <p>A territorial approach is followed in the deployment of circular bioeconomies at regional level, which enables to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Focus on functional distribution of space based on degree of rurality / urbanisation (rural – semirural – peri-urban – urban) ▶ Examine the natural, geographical, economic, social, political features of the region ▶ Examine the central control and the hierarchical organisation of networks within space ▶ Examine how the regional ecosystem is affected by spatial planning policies (regional development plans, urban development plans, etc.) 	<p>Our Objectives</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✔ Deeper understanding of existing bioeconomy governance practices and models in Europe ✔ Enhanced understanding of the bioeconomy's benefits amongst all stakeholders (including primary biomass producers as well as consumers) ✔ Improved regional governance models with increased stakeholder engagement accelerating the circular bioeconomy transition of European regions ✔ Better informed bioeconomy strategies creating conducive conditions for investments in sustainable business opportunities offered by local bio-based economies ✔ Improved environmental footprint of bio-based products and services ✔ Increased cross-regional coordination under the CCRl reinforcing the EU science-policy interface for addressing Sustainable Development Goals
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Figure 22. ROBIN's approach & objectives

• Information about ROBIN partners and Advisory Board members;

About	Concept & Objectives	Activities	Partners	Advisory Board
<p>ARISTOTELEIO PANEPISTIMIO THESSALONIKIS</p>	<p>Research & Academia WP1, WP2</p>			
<p>BIOPRO BADEN-WUERTEMBERG GMBH</p>	<p>ROBIN pilot regions</p>			

Figure 23. ROBIN partners website section

Figure 24. ROBIN's Advisory Board members website section

- **Information about each ROBIN pilot region regarding their:**
 - Status of implementation of the bioeconomy
 - Available feedstocks
 - Bioeconomy related challenges
 - Contact points

Figure 25. ROBIN's pilot regions website section

- **ROBIN's resources (Toolbox, Case studies, Deliverables, Dissemination material, Related projects, Related initiatives);**

Figure 26. ROBIN's resources website section

- Relevant News & Events including the project's Newsletters;

Figure 27. News website section

Figure 28. Events website section

Figure 29. ROBIN's newsletters on the website

Figure 30. ROBIN's 1st Newsletter

Figure 31. ROBIN's 2nd Newsletter

5.2.1.1. Website updates (new)

After the initial launch of ROBIN's website in the first 7 months, and with the aim of enhancing its content and improving the user experience, the WR team implemented several changes and introduced new sections. These new sections include knowledge materials derived from the project's tasks and findings, additional dissemination materials highlighting ROBIN's synergies, and updates in the related projects and initiatives sections.

5.2.1.1.1. Updates and additions on the resources section

- *Interactive map with the 10 identified Case Studies*

Within Task 1.3 from September 2022 to February 2023, ROBIN team has collected 50 good practices for the implementation of regional bioeconomy governance models focusing on regions within and outside the ROBIN regions.

From this initial list, 10 case studies have been selected to showcase how regional government has encouraged social innovation and business models to promote circular bioeconomy. The findings of Task 1.3 have been reported into the [*Deliverable 1.2: Good Governance Practices*](#).

WR team added a new website section under Resources where the user can navigate through an interactive map, created and hosted by Teagasc, with the 10 selected case studies that show best practices in the implementation of regional bioeconomy governance models on a regional basis.

Figure 32. Case Studies

- Public deliverables added

Figure 33. Deliverables section

- Rural Bioeconomy Alliance (RBA) dissemination material added

Figure 34. RBA Poster & Leaflet

- Differentiated and updated sections for Related Projects & Related Initiatives which include all project that ROBIN has a synergy with and all initiatives where ROBIN is part of.

Figure 35. ROBIN's Related Projects website section

Figure 36. Related Projects website section

Figure 37. Related Initiatives website section

Figure 38. ROBIN's related initiatives

5.2.1.2. Website Analytics (new)

For monitoring the website's traffic, we utilise the Google Analytics service. Since the project's Toolbox is integrated into the website, Google Analytics are also used to monitor the Toolbox's traffic analytics which will be included into the KPI "unique visit's to project's website". This tool provides valuable statistics that assist us in optimising the website and our dissemination strategy. More specific metrics, which are monitored as part of the DCP, are detailed in the next sub-sections.

Figure 39. ROBIN's website engagement overview

Figure 40. ROBIN users by country

Figure 41. Toolbox users Dec '23 - Mid-Feb '24

Table 5. Overview of project’s website KPI

Dissemination KPI	Target (M36)	Current status (M18)
Unique visits to project’s website	>10.000	4,209

Overall, it appears that the website has gained interest from various groups of stakeholders around the world. This is evident from the increased number of users and visitors to the ROBIN website. As of the time of composing this deliverable in January 2024, the website

has received more than 24.000 session visits from over 4.000 unique visitors worldwide, resulting in over 8.800 ROBIN page views.

The increased visibility of ROBIN's website can be attributed to several factors, including:

(i) The continuous update of the website with project and external news and events related to ROBIN's progress, internal events, presence in external events and general updates on bioeconomy and regional governance models.

(ii) The integration of the website with the project's SMAs by posting website articles on these platforms.

(iii) The integration of ROBIN's toolbox into the project's website.

(iv) The distribution of the website through engagement and research activities, such as including the website QR-code in the project's presentations and promotional material and in some partners' digital signatures.

The increase in the number of new users in mid-October can be attributed to actions such as the increased posting on all our SMAs (2-3 posts per week) alongside with linking every post to a relevant article on the project's website and the increased reposting of posts from our consortium partners. It is anticipated that as the project advances and ROBIN team deploys regional support actions and tests the Toolbox during the next ROBIN months, website visits will continue to increase.

Furthermore, the content and structure of the website will be constantly updated and enriched in the coming months. These coordinated efforts will enable our team to reach the final website KPIs.

5.2.2. Newsletter (updated)

ROBIN has committed to producing a bi-annual newsletter on a semi-annual basis. So far, two newsletters have been distributed to the project's target audience and uploaded to the project's website. Each newsletter summarizes the updates on the project's progress and actions, providing an alternative way to inform existing subscribers about the project's results. Furthermore, the newsletter serves as a means to attract and retain stakeholders who are not familiar with social media, as well as citizens who may not have been sufficiently interested during the initial phases of the project.

The newsletters were prepared by White Research, with partners contributing specific content when necessary. The Mailchimp platform has been used for the development and distribution of the newsletter, as well as for capturing analytics. The newsletter primarily includes the following sections: (i) an introductory section, (ii) project updates, (iii) information about upcoming events, (iv) details about sister projects, and (v) any other special sections.

Regarding the subscription to the newsletter, all GDPR provisions will be adhered to. Subscribers will be required to agree to the project's Privacy Policy, and they will have the option to unsubscribe from the newsletter at any time.

A dedicated website section at the bottom of the website featuring the ROBIN newsletter subscription has been included to facilitate new subscribers. So far, ROBIN's newsletter has **106** subscribers.

Figure 42. ROBIN newsletter subscription

Figure 43. ROBIN 1st and 2nd Newsletter

Table 6. Overview of newsletters released KPI

Dissemination KPI	Target (M36)	Current status (M18)
Number of newsletters released	6	2

The Newsletter is sent to all the subscribers upon its release and each issue is also uploaded on the project’s website. Overall, the ROBIN newsletter has proven to be an effective channel

for reaching virtual followers. As of the time of writing this deliverable in February 2024, there are more than 100 subscribers to the project's newsletter. With engagement activities expected to intensify after February due to the operationalization of the Regional Support Actions, a continuous increase in subscribers is anticipated.

5.2.3. Social Media Accounts (SMAs) (updated)

ROBIN's SMAs have proven to be valuable tools for consistently promoting the project and its ongoing activities in a visually engaging and interactive manner. ROBIN's Facebook page, Twitter account, LinkedIn profile, and YouTube channel have been established in October 2022 (M2). Given the widespread daily use by our targeted stakeholders, SMAs have been leveraged to the fullest extent, making them essential digital communication channels for the project's efforts to establish and expand its stakeholder base. Furthermore, SMAs facilitate the redirection of the audience to the ROBIN's website, often by promoting existing content from the website, thus playing an integral role in our communication strategy.

The target audiences addressed by each social media channel and the specific objectives are presented in Table 7:

Table 7. The target audiences addressed by each social media channel

Social Network	ROBIN Target Audience	Objectives
Facebook	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Biobased SMEs – Biobased industrial companies – Primary biomass producers <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Investors – Regional bioeconomy actors <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – General public – Consumers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Build a network of followers ✓ Update them on the project's progress and project events ✓ Publish relevant posts
Twitter	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Directorate Generals of the European Commission <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – EU policymakers – National governments – Local governments – Regional authorities <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Policy advisors – Individual researchers – Bioeconomy Clusters - Action Groups 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Communicate key messages and the project's outcomes ✓ Announce project and upcoming events ✓ Retweet relevant content from other Horizon Europe/ H2020 projects

LinkedIn	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – EU policymakers – Policy advisors – Bioeconomy experts – Innovation Advisors – Research Centers – Research groups – Individual researchers <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Universities – International Organisations <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – NGOs – Financial Institutions – Governmental Institutions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Present the project and boost professional and expert discussions
YouTube	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – EU policymakers – Bioeconomy experts – Innovation Advisors <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Investors – Regional bioeconomy actors – Primary biomass producers <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Research Centers – Research groups – Individual researchers <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – General public <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Consumers – Clusters – Action Groups 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Upload promotional video ✓ Contribute to increasing the visibility of the project

WR is responsible for the management of ROBIN's SMAs, while all partners contribute by:

- Becoming a follower (like or follow the page/profile);
- Promoting the accounts in their networks;
- Suggesting relevant profiles that ROBIN should connect with;
- Sharing interesting articles and news to be promoted through the project's SMA;
- Promoting ROBIN posts and news through the SMAs of their own organisations.

To enhance the engagement of our partners in all ROBIN's communication and dissemination activities the WR team has introduced [Trello](#) and has invited all ROBIN partners to use the dedicated workspace (Figure 46). [Trello](#) is a popular project management and collaboration tool that uses a system of boards, lists, and cards to help individuals and teams organize and manage tasks and projects. Team members can be added to boards, lists, and cards, and they can collaborate in real-time by adding comments, attachments, due dates, and more

Figure 44. ROBIN social media posts in Trello

WR team uploads all Social Media posts on a dedicated Trello workspace which is designed for teamwork (Figure 45). All ROBIN partners are able to copy the content of its post and potentially upload it through their organisations SMAs or in other internal communication channels. There is also the option to provide their ideas for future posts (Figure 46).

Figure 45. Trello card dedicated for providing ideas for future posts

Trello is suitable for cross-functional project collaboration, where different teams and stakeholders can have visibility into the project's progress and contribute to the tasks. So far, partners have indicated that they use the Trello board and find it very useful.

5.2.3.1. Facebook (updated)

ROBIN's Facebook page was established in M2. So far, this channel has offered a valuable opportunity to share ROBIN's news and results with followers who are interested in related topics. More specifically, ROBIN's Facebook account serves as a:

- News and discussion hub where information or news related to the project and topics of bioeconomy, and circular economy will be shared;
- Platform to deliver updates about developments and results of the project (e.g., published reports, scientific publications, key events, activities, important achievements);
- Link to other similar groups and pages associated with relevant topics.

Figure 46. Screenshot of ROBIN's Facebook page

Figure 47. ROBIN's Toolbox post

To monitor the performance of the ROBIN page, Facebook Analytics are used.

Figure 48. ROBIN's Facebook page analytics

Overall, the use of Facebook has also been beneficial for sharing news with followers. Since October 2023, 87 posts have been uploaded to ROBIN’s page. We believe that our social media strategy has proven to be successful, resulting in 96 followers as of February 22, 2024, and enabling ROBIN to communicate effectively within the Facebook community. The effectiveness of the account is evident when considering the Facebook metric *Total reach* (3.776 views) which shows the number of people who have seen any Facebook posts within their news feeds, on the ROBIN page, and as shared by their networks. This metric also includes people who do not follow ROBIN on Facebook.

5.2.3.2. X (formerly Twitter) (updated)

Similar to Facebook, the ROBIN Twitter account was launched in October 2022 (M2). Twitter is an essential dissemination tool for ROBIN, as it keeps engaged the ROBIN partners who are very active in using Twitter and enables all followers to stay updated on project news and outcomes of relevant projects. Twitter is an extremely valuable dissemination tool for ROBIN, especially during events where information needs to be immediately publicized.

The Twitter platform also contributes in establishing new synergies with similar initiatives. The use of hashtags allows the project’s messages to reach broader audiences, and the concise and precise text in posts can actively engage a wide range of stakeholders.

In this context, the Twitter account acts as a:

- General dissemination platform that includes the key messages of the project and directs users to other project-related platforms/tools (e.g., ROBIN’s website, newsletter promotional video) and provides information on the project’s development (upcoming events, participation in external events, project results, etc.);
- Newsfeed platform collecting and updating news from other relevant projects and organisations;
- Community of followers interested in the topic and sector.

ROBIN partners contribute to the Twitter account on a regular basis by retweeting its content via their personal accounts and suggesting relevant content. Twitter analytics are used to monitor the account’s performance. A snapshot of the account is provided in Figure 48.

Figure 49. Screenshot of ROBIN's X account

Figure 50. X analytics Nov '23 - Jan '24

In the last three months ROBIN’s Twitter account has garnered more than 4,000 tweet impressions and engaged 318 followers (as of February 22, 2024). The use of Twitter has proven to be a valuable social media channel for reaching a broader community by retweeting news, upcoming events, and project activities. It also enables us to follow interesting conversations on other Twitter accounts and actively participate in them to expand ROBIN’s visibility and network.

5.2.3.3. LinkedIn (updated)

The LinkedIn platform was selected to promote the project to a more professional audience. The profile of the project was set in October 2022 (M2) in order to present the project and offer updates

on its progress. ROBIN partners have been continuously supporting the project’s LinkedIn profile, reposting its content and inviting followers.

The metrics and insights provided by LinkedIn will be utilised to assess the project’s performance.

ROBIN project

Deploying circular bioeconomies at regional level with a territorial approach (2022-2025)

Research Services · Brussels · 528 followers · 11-50 employees

Figure 51. Screenshot of ROBIN's LinkedIn account

Given the professional nature of this social network, ROBIN’s LinkedIn page is more project-focused, and it hosts content that is either directly related to the project (e.g., the project's latest news, progress, upcoming events) or content involving broader developments that are expected to have a direct impact on the project (e.g., important news from the CCRI, relevant EC initiatives). The metrics provided by LinkedIn are being utilised to monitor and assess the project’s performance on this network channel (see Figure 51).

Figure 52. LinkedIn posts impressions (Jan '23 - Jan '24)

Post title	Post type	Audience	Impressions	Views	Clicks	CTR	Reactions
<p> ROBIN project was present at the 4th Symposium on...</p> <p>Posted by Pinelopi Kaslama</p> <p>6/30/2023</p> <p>Get more engagement Boost</p>	Image	All followers	793	-	21	2.65%	30
<p>ROBIN project promotional video</p> <p>Posted by Pinelopi Kaslama</p> <p>6/26/2023</p> <p>Get more engagement Boost</p>	Video	All followers	1,700	-	27	1.59%	37

Figure 53. ROBIN's promotional video impressions

Overall so far, ROBIN has engaged 528 followers on LinkedIn as of February 22, 2024. Through the use of LinkedIn, ROBIN has the opportunity to stay engaged with CCRI developments and participate in professional and expert discussions on issues of common interest within a wide range of professional networks. Additionally, LinkedIn has contributed significantly to introducing ROBIN promotional video to a wider audience by engaging more than 1.700 stakeholders on their feed. It is expected that through this channel, the project's visibility will continue to increase among interested stakeholders in the deployment of regional circular bioeconomy governance models.

5.2.3.4. YouTube (updated)

YouTube has been chosen as the primary digital channel for communicating the identity and goals of the project in a visual way. A YouTube channel for ROBIN has been created in October 2022 (M4) to upload the promotional video and other project-related videos in one easily accessible location, with the aim of enhancing visibility and engaging the audience.

Figure 54, Screenshot of ROBIN's YouTube channel

ROBIN’s promotional video, described in [sub-chapter 5.1.5](#), was uploaded on ROBIN’s YouTube channel [here](#) in May 2023, right after its launch. The promotional video serves as a central feature of ROBIN’s YouTube channel. Project partners are expected to contribute to the production of relevant videos, including script ideas and actual footage, so as to add more videos on ROBIN’s YouTube channel and communicate further ROBIN’s ideas.

As of the writing of this report in February 2024, ROBIN’s YouTube channel had 31 subscribers, while the promotional video had a total of 363 views.

Table 8. Overview of followers on social media KPI

Dissemination KPI	Target (M36)	Current status (M18)
Followers on social media	>1,000	973

5.2.4. Public Deliverables

Another addition in terms of digital dissemination relates to a new section on ROBIN’s website designed to host all of the project’s public deliverables. After communicating with the project officer (PO), the PO permission to ROBIN team to publicly upload and distribute these deliverables. Consequently, each time a public deliverable is submitted, it is uploaded to the website and shared via the project’s social media channels. The dissemination of these deliverables focuses on enhancing the visibility of the project’s scientific results, with a primary focus on academic and policy-oriented audiences. The dissemination through social media allows a broader audience to comprehend the fundamental concepts and purposes of each deliverable.

Figure 54. ROBIN's public deliverables uploaded to the website

5.3. Events (updated)

ROBIN has participated in several events to promote its outcomes and expand its influence on how to deploy regional governance models with a focus on bioeconomy.

5.3.1. Project events (updated)

The events organised in the framework of ROBIN aim to raise awareness around the concept of the project, promote the project's results and facilitate the engagement of key stakeholders which will support the project's activities and provide feedback on the produced outcomes. Several events, such as stakeholder engagement events, mutual learning workshops, and a final dissemination event will promote the exploitation of ROBIN's results.

Throughout the entire ROBIN duration, a series of events will be organised to:

- (i) align ROBIN'S support actions to regional needs (co-creation workshops);
- (ii) design tailored action plans (action plan workshop);
- (iii) catalyse connections and enhance understanding of bioeconomy amongst regional stakeholders (stakeholder engagement events);
- (iv) exchange knowledge across regions (mutual learning workshops);
- (v) build capacity amongst stakeholders around Europe (train-the-trainers event); and
- (vi) disseminate final results (final event in M36).

The following types of events are scheduled as part of the project's plan:

Table 9. ROBIN's internal events

Event	WP, Task, responsible partner	Short description	Date (estimation)	Status
5 regional co-creation events (one in each region) comprised of 2 sessions	WP2, T2.1, CTA, support: all	<p>Session 1: Validation and prioritisation of key barriers, potentialities, and opportunities to be pursued;</p> <p>Session 2: Definition of improvement areas for current governance model(s) & co-creation of new one(s) (including novel business models and social measures)</p>	M1-M15	✓ Done
Action Plan Workshop	WP2, T2.2, CTA, support: all	<p>A workshop where the regional partners will shape Action Plans detailing the specific support actions that will be offered in their region. The concrete output of this task is an Action Plan for each ROBIN region (D2.2)</p>	M10-M16	✓ Done

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Regional partners will run 2 stakeholder engagement events	WP3, T3.2, BPRO, support: all	Events to engage stakeholders in the frame of the support actions where feedback will be collected from major testing	M18-M30	Scheduled
Digital validation workshop	WP3, T3.3, S2I, support: all	Validation workshop of the Toolbox with the Advisory Board	M16-M32	Scheduled
2 mutual learning workshops and missions (DE and SK)	WP4, T4.2, CTA, support: all	In collaboration with the respective regional partners to exchange information	M18-M34	TBD
Train-the-Trainer event	WP4, T4.2, CTA, support: all	An event that will open the way for building the capacity	M18-M34	TBD
Final dissemination event	WP5, T5.1, WR, support: all	Final event and dissemination of ROBIN's results	M36	TBD
<i>In total at least 22 workshops and events will be organised within WP1 – WP5</i>				

So far, until February 2024 (M18) a series of events has been organized and will continue to be organized to fulfil and promote both the project and its outcomes. As of the writing of this document, the first half of the project has been completed, and many of the events originally planned in the first DCP as described above ([Table 6](#)) have already taken place. All partners report their dissemination actions, events and workshops happened in the dissemination reporting template (Figure 55 below).

No. of Action	Date of activity	Place of activity	Type of activity (Choose one of the activity categories listed in the drop-down menu)	of your organization (of conference, workshop, publication, website article, ...)	Scientific Community	Industry	Policy makers	Civil Society	General public	Media	Innovation	Customers	Others	Total	Countries addressed (and "Other" if the latter covers the whole work, apart from the rest of the action counts of EU member states)	of your organization's involvement (by: In-person, attendance, online, discussion, writing, ...)	Type of project material used (e.g., video, infographic, brochure, poster, ROBIN presentation, ...)	Quantity of project material used (% of copies distributed and type of project material used, if not applicable)	Other ROBIN partners or external organisations responsible (limited to: N/A if not applicable)	Short description of the action	Other comments (if relevant)	Significant contacts made (if relevant to dissemination, name, position, organisation, etc. if not)	Press (date, for the week)
1	15/02/2022	Virtual (zoom)	Participation in activities supported by the work under Horizon Europe projects	Implementing circular systems solutions in cities and regions	0	0	0	24	0	0	0	0	0	24	EU-wide	Speaker	N/A	N/A	N/A	Other Horizon Europe Cities projects - round table on introducing ROBIN and results	Participants were introduced to important representatives of cities, regions and other Horizon Europe 8. The participation in the event was essential since the project was introduced to important EU projects, opening new possibilities for cooperation.	N/A	Hanna Heinen (EP)
2	15/02/2022	Workshop	Participation in workshop	J4 CCR Coordination and Support Workshop: Getting started	23	20	80	10	0	0	0	0	0	133	Global	Participant	N/A	N/A	CP, L2	Workshop on the coordination and support of the project. The project was introduced to important EU projects, opening new possibilities for cooperation.	N/A	Marta Rapach (EP)	
3	1/3/2022	Workshop	Participation in workshop	1st Annual Workshop "Projects/Projects" - outcomes and	0	0	0	0	60	0	0	0	0	0	EU-wide	ROBIN partner	1 poster	N/A	N/A	Workshop organized by European Commission Network in collaboration with "Partnership for the Regions, Regions, and Regions".	N/A	Christina Huber (EP)	
4	24/11/2022	On-line	Participation in workshop	AT RECONNECT Final Event	0	0	0	0	35	0	0	0	0	35	EU-wide	Speaker	1 description	N/A	N/A	Participation in the RECONNECT Final Event. The CAP related dissemination actions as ROBIN, CAP related about RECONNECT in a collaborative project.	N/A	Rezaul Karim (EP)	
5	24/11/2022	On-line	Participation in workshop	RECONNECT	0	0	0	0	80	0	0	0	0	80	Global	Speaker	1 description	N/A	N/A	Participation in the RECONNECT webinar. The CAP related dissemination actions as ROBIN, CAP related about RECONNECT in a collaborative project.	N/A	Rezaul Karim (EP)	
6	20/11/2022	Webinar	Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication	National section of Europe's 10 best newspapers on-line and	0	0	0	0	160,000 press members and 7,000,000 other members	0	0	0	0	0	Regional (Denmark, Spain)	Author	N/A	N/A	N/A	Article created to disseminate the project, its goals and impact activities, with wide and relevant impact in Denmark.	N/A	Beatriz Cebalga (EP)	
7	16/1/2023	Online and in-person in Southern Region of Ireland	Press release	Website articles	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	Regional	Author	N/A	N/A	N/A	Two on-line articles published in regional publications highlighting the project's progress.	N/A	Alex Whelan (EP)	
8	20/11/2022	On-line	Press release	Web for the Reconnect occasion (Free European public)	0	0	0	0	6,000	615	0	0	13	6,615	National	Author	1 description	N/A	N/A	Press release sent to the BOPRO's location.	N/A	Rezaul Karim (EP)	

Figure 55. Dissemination reporting template

More specifically:

- **5 regional co-creation events (one in each region) comprised of 2 sessions for Task2.1 in April/May 2023 (M8/M9).**

5 two-part co-creation workshops were organized to first validate and prioritise key barriers, potentialities, and opportunities to be pursued in each ROBIN region and then to define improvement areas for current governance model(s) & co-creation of new one(s) (including novel business models and social measures).

In total, five workshops have been organised, one in each region, overall engaging **69 stakeholders**, including the Multi-Actor Regional Constellations (MARC) members of each pilot region and other regional quadruple helix stakeholders. Explicitly:

- 15 policy makers,
- 17 researchers and academics,
- 12 civil society representatives,
- 23 business and SME representatives.
- 2 Other

Figure 56. Co-creation workshops series

- **Action Plan Workshop for Task 2.2 (M14)**

During the 3rd project meeting in Cork, Ireland (October 2023) all ROBIN partners discussed their ideas to shape regional Action Plans detailing the specific support actions that will be offered in their region.

Figure 57. Action Plan Workshop

Upcoming internal events:

For the remaining 18 months of the project, a series of upcoming events are expected as described in [Table 6](#).

White Research will continue supporting partners for the dissemination and engagement needs of these events, when needed, just as it did during the first half of the project. Additionally, following the conclusion of each event, the organizers should complete the Event Reporting Template, in which they mention the primary communication and/or dissemination actions that occurred. White Research uses this information, in combination with photos or other materials, to promote the event through ROBIN’s SMAs.

Table 10. Overview of project workshops & events KPI

Dissemination KPI	Target (M36)	Current status (M18)
Project workshops & Events	22	6

White Research will maintain its support for the dissemination and engagement aspects of these events, just as it did during the first half of the project. Additionally, following the conclusion of each internal event, the organizers are obligated to complete a template, known as the [Event Reporting Template](#), in which they outline the primary communication and/or dissemination actions that occurred. White Research uses this information, in combination with photos or other materials, to promote the event through ROBIN’s SMAs.

5.3.2. External events and conferences (updated)

Besides attending internal events, ROBIN partners have attended external events such as conferences and workshops with the aim to reach a wide audience relevant to ROBIN’s objectives. During these events the partners:

- Present the project (concept, approach, etc.);
- Promote the project's results;
- Promote ROBIN's actions and events;
- Establish synergies and contacts with relevant projects and initiatives;
- Engage relevant stakeholders in the project's activities;
- Promote the project's dissemination channels (website, SMAs, etc.).

The first version of the DCP had presented an indicative list of identified conferences and events. The updated version of DCP offers a list of external events where ROBIN was presented (Table 7).

The partners participating in external events should always follow the visual identity of the project and use the official promotional material (leaflet, poster, .ppt template, etc.). In case of participation in an external event with the aim to present ROBIN, partners should send the final presentation to WR **at least 5 working days prior to the event**. In addition, the partners should always inform WR in advance regarding their participation in an external event to be appropriately disseminated through the project's dissemination accounts. Finally, after actual participation, partners should fill in the reporting template (Annex I) and send it back to WR.

An indicative list of identified conferences and events is provided below:

Table 11. List of external events where ROBIN partners have participated

No.	Event title	Date	Brief description of ROBIN participation
1	1st CCRI Coordination and Support Workshop: 'Getting started'	October 2022	Participation to a joint workshop with representatives of other Horizon Circular Cities projects. Round table for introducing ROBIN and receive information about the progress of other projects.
2	EuBioNet annual MML workshop "Projects2projects" – outcomes and material	October 2022	Participation to a workshop organised by the EuBioNet in collaboration with the EC and representatives of cities, regions and other Horizon Europe & Horizon 2020 CCRI-CSO. Brief introduction of ROBIN, networking and information exchange with other projects.
3	ATRESBIO Final Event	November 2022	Participation to the ATRESBIO project Final Event. Brief introduction of ROBIN and its bioeconomy objectives.
4	INTERCOONNECTA	November 2022	Participation to the INTERCOONNECTA webinar. Brief introduction of ROBIN and its bioeconomy objectives.

5	Southern Regional Assembly meeting	February 2023	Participation to the Southern Regional Assembly's meeting. Detailed presentation of ROBIN project and engaging discussion for bioeconomy practices with the Southern Regional Assembly Members.
6	TRANSFIERE	February 2023	Participation to the 12th European Meeting on Science, Technology and Innovation, the main R&D&I meeting in Southern Europe. Brief presentation of ROBIN and its relation to bioeconomy.
7	StartUP HUB Educational Conference	February 2023	Participation to the Conference organized by the SmartUp Hub Cluster and supported by the Ministry of Economy of the Slovak republic. Brief introduction of ROBIN and its objectives.
8	CCRI Thematic Working Group - Bioeconomy	March 2023	Participation to the first meeting of the CCRI thematic working group on bioeconomy as a CCRI multiplier.
9	Mainstream Bio 2nd Project Meeting	March 2023	ROBIN flyer included in participants welcome pack.
10	ExpoBiomasa 2023	May 2023	Brief introduction of ROBIN and its objectives.
11	Food 4 Future - Expo FoodTech	May 2023	Presentation of the Andalusian Circular Bioeconomy strategy and the projects in which Andalusia is involved, such as ROBIN.
12	Fomento de la bioeconomía andaluza	July 2023	Brief introduction of ROBIN and its objectives.
13	Transferring experience from international projects to agricultural policy-making	August 2023	Participation to a joint workshop with representatives of other Horizon Europe projects implemented in Slovakia. Presentation of ROBIN and networking with other projects.

14	1st workshop for the development of the national Greek Bioeconomy Hub of Horizon Europe project CEE2ACT	September 2023	Introduction of ROBIN in the 1st national co-creation workshop of the project CEE2ACT for the Greek Bioeconomy Hub, which was organised by CLUBE within the 87th Thessaloniki International Fair (TIF) 2023.
15	Promoting social innovation in Slovakia and the Danube Region	October 2023	Participation to the Slovak event, organized by the Ministry of Investment, Regional Development and Informatization of the Slovak Republic as the National Focal Point for the Interreg Programme of the Danube Region in cooperation with the Ministry of Labour, Social Affairs and Family of the Slovak Republic. Brief introduction of ROBIN and its objectives.
16	Bioeconomy Ireland Week 2023	October 2023	Participation to the launch event <i>Communities, Regions & Cities – The 'Bioeconomy in Action' in your Region</i> of the Bioeconomy Ireland Week 2023. Brief introduction of ROBIN and its objectives.

To ensure consistency in the presentation and participation of ROBIN in external events, partners utilized various dissemination tools including posters, PowerPoint presentations (.ppt), and the project's logo. Partners have also ensured adherence to ROBIN's visual identity. All partners had notified WR beforehand whenever a partner played a key role in an event (e.g., presenter, discussant, co-organizer, etc.), and reported afterwards their dissemination actions in the Event's Reporting Template.

Table 12 provides an indicative list of upcoming events in which ROBIN partners could participate to promote the project.

Table 12. List of upcoming events where ROBIN can/will be presented

Event title	Date	Brief description of ROBIN participation
You(th) in and for bioregions	13.3.2024	The event will be organized as a satellite event of the Bioeconomy Changemakers Festival. The target audience is youth and all activities will be focused on inspiration and motivation of young people and present the opportunities for youth in bioeconomy. ROBIN will have a booth there.

Bioeconomy Career Info Day event	14.3.2024	The event will be organized as a satellite event of the Bioeconomy Changemakers Festival in Thessaloniki and its topic will be informing interested stakeholders for a career in bioeconomy.
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Table 13. Overview of external events/conferences attended KPI

Dissemination KPI	Target (M36)	Current status (M18)
External events/conferences attended	>15	16

During the first 18 months of the project, ROBIN partners participated in 16 external events both virtually and physically. This metric exceeds not only the interim target of 5 events, as initially outlined in the first DCP, but also surpasses the final target of 15 events. In these events, partners played pivotal roles, such as discussants or presenters, maximising the project's visibility. It is evident that participation in external events has proven to be one of the most effective means of disseminating ROBIN to both the EU community and regional audiences, while also establishing a robust audience base. Even though ROBIN has achieved the official KPIs, the ROBIN team will continue participating in external events, as this could result to positive impacts on other KPIs, such as promotional video views, website visits and social media followers.

5.4 Publications

5.4.1. Scientific publications

Scientific publications are important significant channels for presenting ROBIN's outcomes to academic, research, and industrial target audiences. Thus, creating knowledge impact and enabling other researchers and stakeholders to use the project's results in their own work contributes to disseminating the project further.

As set in the initial DCP ROBIN's publications KPI foresees at least 3 scientific publications in the framework of the project. The initial version of the DCP included an indicative list of journals for the dissemination of scientific outputs. As the project has progressed over the first 18 months, ROBIN partners have reported their initial efforts towards scientific publications. Table 14 provides the current status of scientific publications. This matrix was developed by WR and shared with all partners on the project's online repositories on SharePoint and ROBIN's MS Teams platform. It is mandatory for all partners to report their publication efforts and keep the table up to date.

ROBIN publications matrix																				
#	Author(s)	Partner(s)	Title of paper / topic (e.g. bioeconomy, green growth, support tools)	Related ICAM deliverable or result (if any)	Title of the journal/proceedings/ conference series/Book (if applicable)	Status paper	DOI	Type of publication	Repository	Collection	Published	Place Published	Year Published	Is this publication available in Open Access, or a preprint repository?	If Green Open Access, has the article been peer-reviewed?	If Gold Open Access, has the article been peer-reviewed?	Is this a peer-reviewed publication?	Is this a full peer-reviewed publication?	Comments	
1	Alexandros Skordas, Vasilios Ntzou, Ifigenia Skalki, Athina Theodorou, James Guffey, Robert Ludwig, Tracy O'Connor, Eleni Papan, Iyng Goh, Eleonora Thylander	AZITH, MTU, KCM, EPFD	A European comparative study of circular bioeconomy governance strategies and good governance practices for supporting local operators and innovation developers in the circular bioeconomy. (Bioeconomy)	01.1, 01.2	16th Symposium on Circular Economy and Sustainability Innovation, October 29-31, June, 2023	Published	N/A	Publication in Conference proceedings/workshop												
2																				
3																				
4																				
5																				

Figure 55. ROBIN's publication matrix

Since ROBIN's consortium supports open access to scientific publications, all necessary steps will be taken to ensure free access to peer-reviewed articles resulting from the project. Actions in this regard will include the following alternatives as described in the Open Data Strategy of the EC and will follow the FAIR approach. ROBIN's research outputs will be accessible to the public in a digital and online way, and free of charge. Therefore:

- i. Research deliverables will be published on the project's web portal;
- ii. Scientific publications will be immediately open and accessible through a trusted repository (e.g., Open Research Europe, European Open Science Cloud) ("green" or "gold" open access).

Green open access: Deposit an electronic copy of the published version or the final manuscript accepted for publication in a scientific publication relating to the project's foreground in an institutional or subject-based repository at the moment of publication. The beneficiaries will make their best efforts to ensure that this electronic copy becomes freely and electronically available to anyone through this repository within 6 months from the publication date. The exact selection of the repository, the terms under which access will be granted, and all other relevant details will be decided when the publication is available.

Gold open access: Immediately provide the article in open access mode, with the payment of publication costs being shifted away from readers. The costs (Author Processing Charges) will be paid by the partners supporting the research.

Table 14. Overview of scientific publications KPI

Dissemination KPI	Target (M36)	Current status (M18)
Scientific publications	3	1

So far, only 1 publication presented in the 4th Symposium of Circular Economy and Sustainability has been published.

5.4.2. Non-scientific publications

Throughout the duration of the ROBIN project, all partners are invited to produce press and media releases, articles in mass media, and presentations on TV or radio, or other media. The aim of all these efforts is to increase the project's visibility and publicity and the potential to reach out to stakeholders outside of the consortium.

In the initial DCP version was stated that *all partners are responsible for identifying publishing opportunities and for carrying out all necessary actions to ensure the promotion of the project's assets and results.*

To promote the project, partners have made significant contributions, including publishing articles, issuing press releases, and even presenting ROBIN on radio shows and podcasts. Press releases aim to inform stakeholders about the overall project actions and results. Table 15 presents all partners' dissemination efforts that can be grouped under non-scientific publications.

Table 15. Non-scientific publications

Type of non-scientific publications	Amount
Press Releases	13
Presentation of ROBIN on the Radio	1

6. Roles and responsibilities (updated)

The allocation of responsibilities answers the question of **who** is going to implement the DCP. In order to achieve the defined objectives, the implementation of the dissemination and communication strategy is a collective effort from all consortium partners. WR as the dissemination and communication manager monitors the implemented activities and the progress towards the realisation of the DCP objectives. Partners' contribution is a natural by-product of the project's development as most activities, results, milestones, and progress either involve stakeholder engagement and communication or turn into assets that should be adequately promoted. ROBIN partners constantly contribute to the offline activities by organising events, planning dissemination activities, and participating in external events and conferences to raise awareness. In addition, they are involved in online dissemination activities by providing content and promoting the digital dissemination tools of the project. More specifically consortium partners should:

Online dissemination activities

- Continue providing content for the website, SMAs, and the newsletter (The contribution could be a suggestion for a Facebook or Twitter post, an article regarding the project or a relevant topic of the sector, or an interview). The goals are to ensure a constant flow of content around the project's actions and keep our online presence active and useful for the relevant stakeholders.
- Continue promoting the website, SMAs, and newsletter through their network.
- Continue inform the dissemination manager about relevant events or news of the sector that could be used for content creation.

Physical dissemination activities

- Organise events and raise awareness around the project.
- Disseminate the promotional material of the project (leaflet, poster, etc.).
- Ensure the widest dissemination of ROBIN through their participation in external events and conferences and through publications for online/offline sources (websites, newspapers, magazines, etc.).

Activities reporting:

All partners must report the carried-out dissemination and communication activities to the dissemination manager. More information about the process will follow in the respective chapter.

During the initial phase of the project's implementation, all partners supported WR by disseminating ROBIN's SMAs and the project's website through their own networks. The pilot regions in Spain, Slovakia, Greece and Germany and Ireland have been highly active, participating in or organizing local events to promote ROBIN. Considering the significant progress achieved in most of the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), it is clear that the collaborative efforts of the ROBIN consortium have been fruitful. Therefore, the participatory approach of the DCP will continue until the project's conclusion, with all partners sharing responsibility for enhancing the project's visibility.

7. Networks and synergies

ROBIN's Task 5.3 leader is Steinbeis Europe. ROBIN aims to foster collaboration with other pertinent projects and initiatives through a multifaceted approach, encompassing the following strategies:

- Displaying mutual links and logos on the ROBIN website within dedicated sub-categories such as "related projects" and "related initiatives."
- Disseminating joint announcements, including significant events, across various social media platforms.
- Generating announcements on project websites to promote noteworthy events.
- Co-authoring and publishing mutual blog posts to share insights and updates.
- Extending invitations to representatives from other projects to participate in organized events.
- Collaborating on the organization of joint events, such as workshops or roundtables, involving relevant stakeholders.
- Engaging in social media interactions by liking, sharing, reposting, retweeting, and commenting on each other's posts.
- Collaboratively preparing policy briefs and white papers to contribute to shared knowledge.
- Coordinating joint sessions at conferences for the presentation of collective results.
- Organizing online and on-site meetings to foster expanded cooperation and communication.

To start with the process, an online list was created by the task leader to collect relevant initiatives and projects suggested by partners, in total 47 suggestions were received from these 15 priority projects where selected based on the topic and project timeframe.

Collaboration agreements

To formalise these collaborative efforts, a bilateral collaboration agreement template was drafted (**Error! Reference source not found.**). This document serves to articulate, in written form, the anticipated aspects of collaboration between projects, ensuring clarity and alignment in mutual objectives. Bilateral agreements have been signed to with RBA projects, the sister project [*BIOMODEL4REGIONS*](#) and the project [*SUSTCERT4BIOBASED*](#).

Multiple potential joint activities will be also identified throughout the whole duration of the project and will be reported in the respective deliverable. From the initial stages of the project several potential networks and relevant projects have been identified.

Table 16. An indicative list of ROBIN's dissemination networks

Multiplier for dissemination	Partner(s) that act as contact points
ERRIN Circular Bioeconomy working group	CAG, CTA
BIC bioeconomy platform	BIOPRO, CTA, RCM, CAG
Platform of Bioeconomy ERA NET Actions	RCM
S3P Traceability & Big Data	IFA, CTA, CAG
European Cluster Collaboration Platform	CTA
EITFood	CAG
European Committee of Regions	RCM, CAG, SRA, ZSK
SDSN Black Sea	AUTh
European Alliance for Innovation	PED
European Bioeconomy Alliance	RCM
COOPID Bioeconomy Clusters	MTU
European Bioeconomy Network	QPL, WR
Climate Pact Secretariat	PED

The initial list will be constantly updated during the duration of the project in order to identify new opportunities for collaboration.

Table 17. Indicative list with projects for potential synergies

Acronym	Title	Website
Agro2Circular	New ways to upcycle agri-food packaging	https://agro2circular.eu/
TREASoURcE	Boost innovative circular economy practices to make sustainable products the norm	https://treasource.eu/

SYSCHEMIQ	Systemic solutions for the territorial deployment of the circular economy	Under development
BIOMODEL4REGIONS	Supporting the establishment of the innovative governance models in the bio-based economy	https://www.biomodel4regions.eu/
BIOBOOST	Biomass based energy intermediates boosting biofuel production	https://bioboost.eu/

✓ **Collaboration with the Circular Cities and Regions Initiative (CCRI)**

ROBIN has established from the beginning contact with the CCRI coordination and support office (CSO) and it is already included as a CCRI project. Information about the ROBIN has been provided and it is already available on the CCRI website under [this pad](#) (Figure 55):

Figure 56. Screenshot of the ROBIN site on the CCRI website

✓ Participation in CCRI meetings

ROBIN representatives have participated in general meetings organized by the CCRI-CSO as well as the Thematic Working Group on Circular Bioeconomy. The activities are shown in **Error! Reference source not found.8**.

Table 18. CCRI meetings where ROBIN was represented.

Date	Location	Description
19.10.2022	Brussels	1st CCRI Coordination and Support Workshop
27.10.2022	Online	1st CCRI Webinar where the CCRI methodology for implementation of circular economy was presented
08.03.2022	Online	First meeting of the CCRI Thematic Working Group on Circular Bioeconomy
08.11.2023	Brussels	CCRI General Conference with ROBIN poster presentation
9.11.2023	CCRI Workshop	Participation in the discussion of the thematic working group session “Circular bioeconomy”

✓ Planning of further collaborations

The collaborations planned between ROBIN and the CCRI are shown in **Error! Reference source not found.**

Table 19. Plan of future collaborations and input to the CCRI

What	Timeline	Quantification
Input in the CCRI site " Tools and methods " of each of the components of the toolbox	Final version after WP3 testing done	-20 Governance Models -10 Good practices -3 ROBIN Tools -47 support actions
Invitations to EU regions to participate in ROBIN WP3 and WP4 workshops. Invitation published in the CCRI " Events " site	According to WP3 and WP4 time plan for the workshops	Invitation to at least 5 workshops
Participation of ROBIN representatives in future CCRI events (annual conferences, TWG meetings)	When planned by CCRI	At least 2 onsite and 3 online meetings
Invitation to EU regions to participate in events organised by ROBIN partners. Invitation published in the CCRI " Events " site	When informed by ROBIN partners	at least 10 invitations
Share Information in the CCRI website about publications done by ROBIN partners.	When the publications are ready according to the project plan	At least 3 scientific publications and 1 white paper

✓ Rural Bioeconomy Alliance ([RBA](#))

In addition to the bilateral agreements, ROBIN is also part of the Rural Bioeconomy Alliance ([RBA](#)), which is a cluster of 11 projects (to date), aiming to speed up growth of bioeconomy by sharing knowledge on project outcomes and supporting dissemination and communication activities related to the existing knowledge of bioeconomy. The list of the project members (besides ROBIN) is shown in **Error! Reference source not found.**

Table 20. Projects member of the Rural Bioeconomy Alliance (RBA)

No.	Project	Website
1	BioRural	BioRural - Accelerating circular bio-based solutions integration in European rural areas
2	MainstreamBIO	Mainstreambio project – Mainstreaming small scale Bio-based solutions across rural Europe (mainstreambio-project.eu)
3	P2GreenN	Home - P2Green Project

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4	RELIEF	<u>Relief – euRopean bio-Economy ALLiancE in Farming (uop.gr)</u>
5	RuralBioUp	<u>Home - RuralBioUp</u>
6	SCALE-UP	<u>Home - www.scaleup-bioeconomy.eu</u>
7	COOPID	<u>COOPID Home - COOPID</u>
8	ShapingBio	<u>Shaping Bio</u>
9	BIOMODEL4REGIONS	<u>BIOMODEL4REGIONS Project</u>
10	CEE2ACT	<u>CEE2ACT – CEE2ACT is empowering countries in Central Eastern Europe and beyond</u>

ROBIN has been also included as partner project in [European Bioeconomy Network](#) (**Error! Reference source not found.**)

Figure 57. European Bioeconomy Network

✓ **Other collaboration activities**

- Relevant [projects](#) and [initiatives](#) were displayed and updated in the ROBIN website(**Error! Reference source not found.**)

Figure 58. Screenshot of the ROBIN site where the related projects and initiatives are displayed

- Continuous participation in the meetings of the Rural Bioeconomy Alliance (RBA)
- A presentation about ROBIN was held in the Joint Seminar “Stakeholder engagement in bioeconomy related projects” organised by the projects Biomodel4regions and CEE2ACT. Online/22.06.2023
- Bilateral online meetings were scheduled with the project BIOMODEL4REGIONS to discuss collaboration possibilities continuously.

KPI Status

Table 21. Overview of synergies KPI

Dissemination KPI	Target (M36)	Current Status (M17)
Contributions to the CCRI	50	5
Synergies with initiatives & networks	15	13

The initial list will be constantly updated during the duration of the project in order to identify new opportunities for collaboration.

Table 22. Indicative list with projects for potential synergies

Acronym	Title	Website
Agro2Circular	New ways to upcycle agri-food packaging	https://agro2circular.eu/

TREASoURcE	Boost innovative circular economy practices to make sustainable products the norm	https://treasource.eu/
SYSCHEMIQ	Systemic solutions for the territorial deployment of the circular economy	Under development
BIOMODEL4REGIONS	Supporting the establishment of the innovative governance models in the bio-based economy	https://www.biodel4regions.eu/
BIOBOOST	Biomass based energy intermediates boosting biofuel production	https://bioboost.eu/

A template of a collaboration agreement has been prepared to establish cooperation with other projects and initiatives. Both the template and the signed collaboration agreement with BIOMODEL4REGIONS project for joint dissemination and communication activities, can be found in Annex II.

8. Set up and operation of ROBIN's Advisory Board (updated)

One of the first tasks of ROBIN was to set up an Advisory Board to act as an external consultation body to the project and share its knowledge and expertise with the partners of the project at key stages of its implementation. In fact, following a tailored set up process (see Figure 56), the ROBIN AB has been started to be composed, ensuring diverse expertise, gender mix and geographic spread among the members.

Figure 58. ROBIN Advisory Board set-up process

The members ROBIN's Advisory Board:

- act as a consultation body for the ROBIN consortium, providing the consortium with strategic guidance and feedback in key stages of the project;
- navigate the implementation of the ROBIN Toolbox;
- provide their feedback and expertise on the monitoring and evaluation framework to be used after the pilots;
- facilitate access and extend the reach of our consortium to important European stakeholder communities;
- support the wide-spread acceptance and replication of our activities, by acting as project ambassadors who will inform and invite their networks to benefit from them when they are available.

Moreover, the engagement of the AB members in project activities provides ROBIN with access to additional expertise on top of that of the project partners, fueling the development of both technical and strategic results with a strong value as well as consolidating as best as possible the outcomes of the project.

In this context, the process followed to set up the ROBIN AB is described in further detail within the sections that follow.

8.1. Nominations of experts and final selection (updated)

The setting up of the ROBIN Advisory Board (AB) follows an open and transparent process. Experts active in the academia, civil society, private as well as public sector were identified from the professional networks of ROBIN project partners. In fact, each project partner was asked to identify

and nominate between 2 and 3 experts. Partners were encouraged to propose candidates from other regions/countries than ROBIN's pilot regions, as many stakeholders from the regions are mobilised under WP1.

These experts were nominated considering a set of AB member nomination principles, as presented below.

- **The candidates should be in a good working relationship with at least one consortium partner, albeit external to the consortium;**
- **The AB shall be composed of experts from different sectors (e.g., business community, academia, civil society, governmental bodies) with diverse expertise, gender mix and geographic spread;**
- **The experts who will comprise the AB should have very good knowledge and experience in at least one or more of ROBIN fields (i.e., bioeconomy, regional governance and social innovation);**

The nomination phase was finalised and the project partners together identified and nominated over 25 experts across Europe. The pool of experts nominated by the project partners served as a starting point to select the members of the AB. All partners provided publicly available information (i.e., Name, Organization, Position and Contact Details - email) about the nominated experts.

The next steps followed was the assessment phase where a preliminary screening of the candidates was performed by WR team, ensuring all the forementioned criteria. WR assessed the nominees and shortlisted 11 individuals from the initial list of 25 by:

- Taking into consideration how relevant to ROBIN is their either technical or scientific and/or bioeconomy expertise;
- Respecting the gender balance;
- Respecting the Quadruple Helix stakeholders element;

Each region is represented by a minimum of two AB members, with the regions of Andalusia in Spain and Zilina in Slovakia each being represented by three members. Subsequently, the regional partners who nominated these experts distributed to the selected individuals the Terms of Reference for their participation in ROBIN's Advisory Board. These terms, developed by WR, describe the role, contribution, and benefits of the AB members. Those experts who accepted ROBIN's invitation provided a signed Declaration of Acceptance, which officially indicates their membership in ROBIN's AB.

8.2. Final composition of the Advisory Board (new)

The final composition of ROBIN's AB including their affiliated organisations are the following:

Table 23. ROBIN's Advisory Board members and affiliation

No	First name	Last name	Affiliation
1	Anna	Tenhunen	CLIC (Finnish cluster for bioeconomy) and VTT
2	Vasileios	Filippou	Energy Community of Karditsa
3	María del Mar	Delgado	University of Cordoba (Spain)

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4	José Luis Cruz	Maceín	Madrid Institute of Rural, Agricultural and Food Research and Development (IMIDRA)
5	Prof Maeve	Henchion	Teagasc
6	Marco	Rupp	Bio-based Industries Consortium (BIC)
7	Adriano	Raddi	Government of Catalonia
8	Dr. Ioannis	Bakouros	Management of Technology Research Lab (MATER Lab), University of Western Macedonia, Greece
9	Piergiuseppe	Morone	Unitelma Sapienza – University of Rome
10	Chiara	Pocaterra	APRE - Agenzia per la Promozione della Ricerca Europea
11	Jan	Plesnik	National Recycling Agency (NARA SK)

ROBIN’s website includes a website section (as describes in sub-chapter 5.2.1) dedicated to ROBIN’s AB members introducing:

- ✓ Their full names
- ✓ Affiliation
- ✓ Short Bio
- ✓ Their organisations’ link

Figure 59. ROBIN's advisory board

Table 24. Advisory Board achievement indicator

Achievement indicator	Status
ROBIN Advisory Board / Members: 1 / > 10	✓ Achieved

8.3 Operation of the Advisory Board (updated)

As described above at the beginning of chapter 8, ROBIN’s AB mainly acts as a consultation body and provides feedback in specific ROBIN activities. However, throughout the first half of ROBIN, AB members:

- ✓ **Participated online and introduced themselves at ROBIN’s 2nd Project Meeting in Seville, Spain (14-15.03.2023);**
- ✓ **Participated online at ROBIN’s 3rd Project Meeting in Cork, Ireland (4-5.10.2023);**
- ✓ **Were invited to external events where ROBIN was presented such as Ireland Bioeconomy Week 2023.**

ROBIN’s interdisciplinary AB in bioeconomy, regional governance and social innovation, being a multistakeholder consultative body, will play a key role in the deployment of many project’s activities, such as navigating the implementation of the ROBIN Toolbox, uptake of replication guidelines, and synergising actions. Specifically, AB members will play a key role during WP3 where the team evaluates and validates the testing results with the AB to improve the Toolbox (**T3.3**). T3.3 will maintain and fine-tune the **Toolbox** and its constituent tools building on feedback collected in T3.2. Regional partners will administer the feedback collection tools foreseen in the validation plan of their region to alpha and beta testers to capture their feedback. Data collected this way will be analysed to draw meaningful conclusions on areas of improvement for our Toolbox and its components. These will be discussed and validated with AB members in the framework of a digital validation workshop.

Additionally, ROBIN's Advisory Board (AB) members are currently and will continue to be invited to external events where our partners participate, as per our partners' requests.

9. Monitoring, Evaluation, and reporting framework

9.1. Monitoring and evaluation (updated)

The monitoring mechanisms are crucial to secure the successful implementation of the D&C strategy and ensure the achievement of the DCP goals: in essence, they measure the impact of the dissemination efforts. Therefore, a monitoring process has been set up at the beginning of the project. This process supports us to identify any potential gaps and problems, the special needs of relevant stakeholders, and good practices that we can adopt. The DCP will be updated - if needed - to include all the modifications and changes due to the monitoring process. In this way, we aim to ensure the effective dissemination of the outcomes to the project's key stakeholders and the general public.

A set of KPIs was selected to evaluate the impact of the DCP activities. Of course, the metric targets and the needs will be adjusted to the project's results and will be included in the updated deliverable (M36). The dissemination manager with the support of the consortium partners will keep track of the quantitative metrics during the reporting periods.

Below is presented the list of KPIs for the dissemination and communication activities of ROBIN in M18:

Table 25. Key Performance Indicators

Assessed element	Metric	Target (M36)	Current Status (M18)
Unique visits to the project website	Nr. of visits (total)	> 10,000	4.200
Social media accounts (LinkedIn, YouTube, Facebook, Twitter)	Nr. of followers	> 1,000	973
Newsletter	Nr. of published Newsletters	6	2
Project workshops and events	Nr. of workshops	≥ 22	6
Participation in external events/ conferences	Nr. of events	≥ 15	16
Views of the promotional video	Nr. of views (total)	> 500	363
Synergies with initiatives & networks	Nr. of joint actions	15	13
Scientific publications	Nr. of scientific publications	3	1
Promotional material distributed	Nr. of promotional material distributed	>300	302

<i>Stakeholders engaged in overall</i>	Nr. of stakeholders engaged	3.000	>15.000
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9.4. Reporting

Keeping track of the dissemination, communication, and engagement activities that were carried out by all partners in the framework of the project is fundamental for its successful implementation. Therefore, reporting and documentation are very important for the DCP. In particular, throughout the duration of the project, all consortium partners should report their dissemination and communication activities on an ad-hoc basis by filling in the template shared by WR (online in the project's repository) each time they perform a dissemination activity. Each semester (M6, M12, M18, M24, M30, M36) WR consolidates the results and develops the semestrial technical reporting of WP6.

For keeping track of the activities performed by the consortium partners, a reporting template has been designed and shared (Annex).

Table 26. Annex for Dissemination

Annex	Dissemination Tool	Coverage	When
Annex I	Dissemination reporting template	All dissemination activities carried out by the partners every month.	Ad-hoc basis throughout the project

Dissemination reporting template: This template will record all the dissemination and communication activities of the project. The document should be updated by all partners on an ad-hoc basis. Keeping track of the activities will ensure that any problems or gaps will be observed early, and mitigation measures will be put in place in order to be solved. Partners are requested to fill out the form **within 5 days** for any dissemination and communication activity they are involved in. Also, partners are encouraged to inform WR when an event is scheduled and share some brief information (e.g., event, location, dates) as well as take photos & keep the agenda.

Each project partner should immediately contact WR, should any risks be identified concerning communication and dissemination activities, or in case problems arise during the implementation of publicity actions.

10. Timeline and implementation plan

The dissemination and communication activities started at the beginning of the project with the production of the promotional material, will continue with a wide deployment of offline and online dissemination activities, and will be completed with the promotion of the project's final results. On top of that, the project's findings will be promoted even after the end of the project. Figure 60 presents the four different periods during which all our dissemination and communication activities will be implemented.

Figure 60. Summary of ROBIN's timeline

❖ First phase – Early in the project (M1-M6):

During the first phase of the project, the D&C strategy was designed. In the framework of the D&C strategy, several key aspects were identified such as the targeted stakeholder groups that will be reached during the project, as well as the messages that will be used to engage them. In addition, the selection of suitable metrics for monitoring the successful implementation of the strategy took place, and the consortium partners' responsibilities were clearly defined. Besides developing the D&C strategy, the first months of the project were dedicated to the production of the dissemination material, as well as the establishment of the dissemination and communication tools. The project's visual identity and logo, the promotional material (leaflet, poster, templates, letterhead), the SMAs, and the project's website was developed in the first 4 months of the project. Finally, the first dissemination of the project to the broader public took place through contacts with other projects, press releases, our newsletters, the continuous posting on our SMAs and by participating in external events.

❖ Second phase – During the project (M7 - M25):

Throughout the project, constant interaction between the project partners and the relevant stakeholders has been established. An active community interested in the ROBIN project has been created and maintained through the SMAs. In addition, synergies are developed with other projects and initiatives relevant to the topics of bioeconomy, sustainability and circular economy, and regional development. Multiple activities have already taken place and are planned to take place within the second phase of the project including dissemination events, workshops, webinars, meetings with the CCRI-CSO, mutual learning workshops, joint events, and dissemination activities with the sister projects. Publications and promotion of the project's results through the website and the bi-annual Newsletter has further maximised the project's impact. Finally, the participation of consortium partners in external events and conferences, as well as their connections to key networks from the sector is leveraged in order to promote the project to a wider audience.

❖ Third phase – End of the project (M26 - M36):

Although the dissemination of the project's vision will continue, this phase of the project will mainly focus on the dissemination of the project's results and outcomes. In particular, toward the end of the lessons learned will permit consortium partners to draft some key recommendations that can support the adoption of sustainability certification schemes. The project's community will be further engaged to ensure its continuation after the project's completion. Furthermore, a final event will be organised aiming to present the project's results, diffuse the knowledge and engage relevant stakeholders in the post-project exploitation of the findings.

❖ Fourth phase – Beyond the end of the project:

The ambition of ROBIN'S consortium is to continue promoting the project's vision and results even after the official end of the project ensuring that the project's outcomes will reach as many relevant stakeholders as possible. Relevant publications will further disseminate the project's legacy even after the official completion.

11. Conclusions – Way Forward (updated)

A well-designed, clear, and robust dissemination and communication strategy is key for raising awareness of the ROBIN and its expected outcomes. This document outlined among others the communication tools and channels used for maximising ROBIN's visibility, presented the so-far progress of the project in terms of KPIs and provided thorough details in all aspects of ROBIN's communication and dissemination strategy.

The exceptional performance of ROBIN's KPIs and the engagement rates of users on our website and SMAs show the positive results of ROBIN's communication and dissemination strategy ensuring the project's maximum visibility. WR team will be closely monitoring the effectiveness of all partners dissemination efforts, continuously promoting ROBIN's presence internal and external events and will keep up engaging all interested stakeholders with information and activities related to ROBIN's toolbox.

Given the bottom-up, open nature of the project and its activities, the strategy might undergo continuous updates based on feedback, as well as the needs and perspectives of stakeholders. The final version of the Dissemination and Communication Plan and Results will be delivered at the end of the project, reflecting potential ad-hoc adjustments and updates on ROBIN's strategy that might happen throughout the 2nd half of ROBIN's life, presenting the communication and dissemination results of our 36-months strategy and the final status of ROBIN's KPIs.

Annexes

Annex I. Dissemination Reporting Template

Title	Deploying circular bioeconomies at regional level with a territorial approach
Acronym	ROBIN
Start	01/03/2022 (M1)
End	31/03/2025 (M36)
Notes:	Please fill out the form within 5 days for any dissemination and communication activity you carry out

The form below has been designed to help you keep track of any kind of communication and dissemination activity you will carry out throughout the project. Dissemination activities include, but are not limited to, press releases, social media posts, website articles, interviews, events (conferences, seminars, workshops, etc.).
 Important: Specify the type of activity as well as the type of the audience(s) addressed using the categories provided in the drop-down menu. These are the categories used in the Participant Portal by the European Commission and it is important that we stick to them.

No. of Action	Date of activity	Place of activity	Type of activity <i>(Choose one of the activity categories listed in the drop-down menu)</i>	Title of conference, workshop, publication, website article, etc.	Size of audience reached per type of stakeholder (in numbers)										Countries addressed <i>(use "global" if the action covers the whole world, use "EU-wide" if the action covers all EU Member States)</i>	Role and description of your organisation's involvement <i>(e.g. facilitator, interviewer, speaker, discussion leader)</i>	Type of project material used <i>(e.g. ROBIN leaflet, ROBIN poster, ROBIN presentation, etc.)</i>	Quantity of project material used <i>(no. of copies distributed per type of project material, use N/A if not applicable)</i>	Other ROBIN partners or external organisations responsible if involved <i>(use N/A if not applicable)</i>	Short description of the action	Other comments <i>(IF RELEVANT)</i>	Significant contacts made if and share data was given <i>(name, position, organisation, tel, e-mail)</i>	
					Scientific Community	Industry	Policy makers	Civil Society	General public	Media	Investors	Customers	Others	Total									
1	Example 10/13/2022	Virtual (zoom)	Participation in activities organized jointly with other Horizon Europe projects	<i>"Implementing circular systemic solutions in cities and regions"</i>	0	0	0	24	0	0	0	0	0	0	24	EU-wide	Speaker	N/A	N/A	N/A	Participation to a joint workshop with representatives of other Horizon Circular Cities projects. Round table for introducing ROBIN and receive information about the progress of other projects.	The participation in the event was successful since the project was introduced to important CS projects, opening new possibilities for synergies.	N/A

Annex III. Collaboration Agreement

a) Template

Collaboration Agreement

between

	<Insert logo of project/ initiative>
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This Collaboration Agreement is signed between:

- 1. ROBIN “Deploying circular Bioeconomies at Regional level with a territorial approach” EU-funded project under grant agreement 101060504**, represented for the purposes of signing this Collaboration Agreement by Ioanna Nydrioti (WR, WP leader)
- 2. <Insert name of project/initiative>**, represented for the purposes of signing this Collaboration Agreement by <Insert name of the person who will sign this agreement on behalf of the project/ initiative>

The Parties signing this Collaboration Agreement aim to establish a strong liaison between the two projects/initiatives, in terms of bilaterally implementing the following agreed actions. This agreement shall be into force during the agreed period or until termination of the agreement by either Party.

Now, therefore, it is hereby agreed as follows:

WR on behalf of ROBIN agrees to the following:

- Display <Insert project/ initiative> link and logo on the ROBIN website (in a sub-category in the menu, e.g. “similar projects” or “collaboration with other projects”).
 - Distribute <Insert project/ initiative> announcements (e.g. important events) on the ROBIN’s social media platforms.
 - Create announcements on the ROBIN website to promote important <Insert project/ initiative> events.
 - Publish <Insert project/ initiative> (guest) blog posts on the ROBIN’s blog.
 - Invite <Insert project/ initiative> representatives to participate in events organized by ROBIN.
 - Work with <Insert project/ initiative> to create an event (workshop/roundtable with relevant stakeholders) together.
-

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- Like, share (repost, retweet etc.), comment posts of <Insert project/ initiative> on ROBIN social media.
- Joint preparation of policy briefs/white papers.
- Joint organisation of common sessions in conferences where results of ROBIN and <Insert project/initiative> will be presented.
- Joint organisation of online and on-site meetings to expand cooperation.

<Insert name of organisation> **on behalf of** <Insert project/ initiative> **agrees to the following:**

- Display ROBIN link and logo on the <Insert project/ initiative> website (in a sub-category in the menu, e.g. “similar projects” or “collaboration with other projects”).
- Distribute ROBIN announcements (e.g. important events) on the <Insert project/ initiative> social media platforms.
- Create announcements on the <Insert project/ initiative> website to promote important ROBIN events.
- Publish ROBIN (guest) blog posts on the <Insert project/ initiative> blog.
- Invite ROBIN representatives to participate in events organized by <Insert project/ initiative>.
- Work with ROBIN to create an event (workshop/roundtable with relevant stakeholders together).
- Like, share (repost, retweet etc.), comment posts of ROBIN on <Insert project/ initiative> social media.
- Joint preparation of policy briefs/white papers.
- Joint organisation of common sessions in conferences where results of <Insert project/ initiative> and ROBIN will be presented.
- Joint organisation of online and on-site meetings to expand cooperation.

Duration:

- Starting from <insert effective date> and ending on the <insert end date>.

Termination:

- Either Party may terminate this Collaboration Agreement immediately by notice upon the other Party.

ROBIN

Per:

Name:

Ioanna Nydrioti

Title:

Project Manager White Research

ROBIN's WP leader DEC

<Insert project/ initiative>

Per:

Name:

Title:

b) Collaboration Agreement with BIOMODEL4REGIONS

Collaboration Agreement

between

This Collaboration Agreement is signed between:

1. ROBIN “Deploying circular Bioeconomies at Regional level with a territorial approach” EU-funded project under grant agreement 101060504, represented for the purposes of signing this Collaboration Agreement by Ioanna Nydrioti (WR, WP leader)
2. BIOMODEL4REGIONS, represented for the purposes of signing this Collaboration Agreement by Karolina Jurkiewicz (APRE, Task leader of Task 6.4 ‘Clustering with other projects and initiatives’)

The Parties signing this Collaboration Agreement aim to establish a strong liaison between the two projects/initiatives, in terms of bilaterally implementing the following agreed actions. This agreement shall be into force during the agreed period or until termination of the agreement by either Party.

Now, therefore, it is hereby agreed as follows:

WR on behalf of ROBIN agrees to the following:

- Display BIOMODEL4REGIONS link and logo on the ROBIN website (in a sub-category in the menu, e.g. “similar projects” or “collaboration with other projects”).
- Distribute BIOMODEL4REGIONS announcements (e.g. important events) on the ROBIN’s social media platforms.
- Create announcements on the ROBIN website to promote important BIOMODEL4REGIONS events.
- Publish BIOMODEL4REGIONS (guest) blog posts on the ROBIN’s blog.
- Invite BIOMODEL4REGIONS representatives to participate in events organized by ROBIN.
- Work with BIOMODEL4REGIONS to create an event (workshop/roundtable with relevant stakeholders) together.
- Like, share (repost, retweet etc.), comment posts of BIOMODEL4REGIONS on ROBIN social media.
- Joint preparation of policy briefs/white papers.
- Joint organisation of common sessions in conferences where results of ROBIN and BIOMODEL4REGIONS will be presented.

- Joint organisation of online and on-site meetings to expand cooperation.

APRE on behalf of BIOMODEL4REGIONS agrees to the following:

- Display ROBIN link and logo on the BIOMODEL4REGIONS website (in a sub-category in the menu, e.g. “similar projects” or “collaboration with other projects”).
- Distribute ROBIN announcements (e.g. important events) on the BIOMODEL4REGIONS social media platforms.
- Create announcements on the BIOMODEL4REGIONS website to promote important ROBIN events.
- Invite ROBIN representatives to participate in events organized by BIOMODEL4REGIONS.
- Work with ROBIN to create an event (workshop/roundtable with relevant stakeholders together).
- Like, share (repost, retweet etc.), comment posts of ROBIN on BIOMODEL4REGIONS social media.
- Joint preparation of policy briefs/white papers.
- Joint organisation of common sessions in conferences where results of BIOMODEL4REGIONS and ROBIN will be presented.
- Joint organisation of online and on-site meetings to expand cooperation.

Duration:

- Starting from 1. December.2022 and ending on the 31. August.2025.

Termination:

- Either Party may terminate this Collaboration Agreement immediately by notice upon the other Party.

ROBIN

Per:

Name:
Ioanna Nydrioti

Title:
Project Manager White Research (WR)
ROBIN's WP leader DEC

Signature:

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to be 'Ioanna Nydrioti', with a period at the end.

BIOMODEL4REGIONS

Per:

Name: Karolina Jurkiewicz

Title: Project Manager, APRE

Signature:

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to be 'K. Jurkiewicz', on a light blue background.

DEPLOYING CIRCULAR BIOECONOMIES AT
REGIONAL LEVEL WITH A TERRITORIAL APPROACH

About the project

Europe's regional authorities have a crucial role to play as agents of inclusive and resilient economic development for their territories. ROBIN sets out to empower them to fulfil this role with support to co-shape their governance structures in to accelerate the deployment of their circular bioeconomy targets, while also promoting social innovation. We demonstrate the potential of innovative circular bioeconomy governance structures and models in 5 regions within Ireland, Germany, Spain, Slovakia and Greece. We set-up Multi-Actor Regional Constellations engaging key stakeholders to co-create novel governance structures, well-embedded within existing structures of our regions and mandated to execute circular bioeconomy strategies and to coordinate effectively with the Circular Cities and Regions Initiative – Coordination and Support Office (CCRI-CSO). We also provide them with tailored support for enhanced stakeholder engagement, as well as a practical toolbox to improve the operation and monitoring of their models. In the process we coordinate our actions with the CCRI-CSO.

Partners	URL
Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL ADVISORS PC	www.qplan-intl.gr
FUNDACION CORPORACION TECHNOLOGICA SE ANDALUCIA	www.corporaciontecnologica.com
WHITE RESEARCH SRL	www.white-research.eu
PEDAL CONSULTING SRO	www.pedal-consulting.eu
STEINBEIS 2I GMBH	www.steinbeis-europa.de
ROZVOJOVA AGENTURA ZILINSKEHO SAMOSPRAVNEHO KRAJA NO	www.razsk.sk
MUNSTER TECHNOLOGICAL UNIVERSITY	www.circbio.ie
ARISTOTELEIO PANEPISTIMIO THESSALONIKIS	www.auth.gr
REGION OF CENTRAL MACEDONIA	www.pkm.gov.gr
CONSEJERÍA DE AGRICULTURA, PESCA, AGUA Y DESARROLLO RURAL	www.juntadeandalucia.es
INSTITUTO ANDALUZ DE INVESTIGACION Y FORMACION AGRARIA PESQUERA ALIMENTARIA Y DE LA PRODUCCION ECOLOGICA	www.juntadeandalucia.es
BIOPRO BADEN-WUERTTEMBERG GMBH	www.bio-pro.de
SOUTHERN REGIONAL ASSEMBLY	www.southernassembly.ie

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VISIT: www.robin-project.eu

